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Numerical Modeling of Spark Ignition in Internal Combustion
Engines

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Abstract

The aim of this work is to develop a new and comprehensive spark ignition model for 3D CFD combustion modeling in Spark Ignition (SI) engines. The literature review on the experimental and numerical investigations of the spark ignition shows that although this process is well-understood, its complexity makes its modeling a very challenging task. The detailed description of all the phenomena occurring during the spark ignition would require resolving very short time and length scales on very fine numerical meshes, which may not be practical in commercial engineering applications. Usually, simplified phenomenological models of the spark ignition and early flame propagation are developed. The review of the spark ignition models for 3D CFD combustion modeling reveals that in the individual models only particular aspects of the ignition phenomenon are described in detail, while others are taken into account in a very simplified way or even completely omitted. This shows that there is still space for improvements in the field of spark ignition modeling and it is desirable to develop new and more accurate ignition models.

The ignition model for SI engines presented in this work integrates sub-models for individual phenomena of the spark ignition process. The sub-models for the electrical circuit of the ignition system, for the spark plasma dynamics, for the heat transfer from the spark towards surrounding mixture, for the ignition delay of the mixture and for the early flame kernel growth are coupled together to form one comprehensive ignition model. The model is implemented into the AVL FireTM CFD solver in the context of the G -equation combustion model and allows to predict the temporal development and deflection of the spark plasma channel, the ignition delay time and the position of the initial flame kernel. In comparison to other approaches, a more detailed physical model is developed to accurately describe each phenomenon and gain a more complete understanding of the spark ignition process in SI engines.

The performance of the new model is numerically verified by comparing calculated results to experimental data in various cases. The results of the spark discharge modeling in a strong flow field confirm that the model correctly predicts the duration of the discharge process with multiple breakdowns, the deflection of the spark during the first breakdown of the spark arc, the current and the voltage in the electrical circuit and the energy supplied to the spark arc. The results of the spark ignition and combustion modeling in the AVL single cylinder research engine show that the flow field generated in the cylinder during the scavenging and compression processes can considerably deflect the spark arc during the ignition process. The new ignition model is capable of predicting the spark deflection and the actual ignition point dragged away from the spark electrodes. The numerical pressure profile in the cylinder and the Rate of Heat Release (ROHR) also matches the measurement with a good agreement, which proves that the ignition model correctly predicts the ignition process, while the combustion model provides correct flame propagation. Finally, the ignition model is used for modeling the ignition and flame propagation from two spark plugs in the PAMAR-4 Opposed-Piston research engine. The numerical pressure profile in the cylinder and the ROHR are again in agreement with the measurements which shows that the new ignition model is able to correctly predict the ignition of the air-fuel mixture from multiple spark plugs at discrete locations in the combustion chamber, while the G -equation combustion model can handle the flame propagation of the distinct flame fronts coming from multiple ignition points.

Keywords: spark ignition, combustion modeling, AVL FireTM, Internal Combustion Engines

Streszczenie

Celem tej pracy jest stworzenie nowego modelu zapłonu iskrowego do celów modelowania spalania w silnikach o Zapłonie Iskrowym (ZI). Przegląd literaturowy na temat badań eksperymentalnych i numerycznych zapłonu iskrowego pokazuje, że złożoność tego procesu prowadzi do trudności w jego dokładnym opisie numerycznym. Zamodelowanie wszystkich zjawisk fizycznych zachodzących podczas zapłonu iskrowego wymaga rozwiązania bardzo krótkich skal czasowych i skal długości na gęstych siatkach numerycznych, co może okazać się niepraktyczne w zastosowaniach inżynierskich. Tym samym najczęściej rozwijane są uproszczone modele fenomenologiczne zapłonu iskrowego oraz początkowego wzrostu jądra płonienia. Porównanie dostępnych modeli zapłonu iskrowego pokazuje, że poszczególne z nich opisują w sposób dokładny tylko wybrane aspekty zjawiska zapłonu, upraszczając lub całkowicie pomijając pozostałe. Tym samym potrzebne jest rozwijanie nowych modeli, które w sposób bardziej dokładny opiszą zjawisko zapłonu w silnikach ZI.

Nowy model zapłonu iskrowego przedstawiony w tej pracy składa się z kilku modeli opisujących poszczególne zjawiska procesu zapłonu — modelu obwodu elektrycznego układu zapłonowego, modelu dynamiki łuku elektrycznego, modelu wymiany ciepła pomiędzy łukiem elektrycznym a mieszaniną palną, modelu czasu opóźnienia zapłonu mieszaniny palnej oraz modelu wczesnego wzrostu jądra płomienia. Razem tworzą one jeden spójny model zapłonu iskrowego, który został zaimplementowany w kodzie obliczeniowej dynamiki płynów AVL FireTM w kontekście modelu *G*-equation do obliczeń spalania w silnikach ZI. Nowy model przewiduje odkształcenie łuku elektrycznego podczas procesu zapłonu, opóźnienie pomiędzy początkiem wyładowania a rzeczywistym zapłonem mieszaniny oraz położenie pierwszego jądra zapłonu. W porównaniu do innych modeli zapłonu, model przedstawiony w tej pracy w dokładny sposób opisuje indywidualne zjawiska zapłonu iskrowego, przez co pozwala na bardziej dokładną analizę i większe zrozumienie procesów zachodzących w silnikach ZI.

Poprawność przedstawionego modelu została zweryfikowana poprzez porównanie otrzymanych wyników numerycznych z wynikami eksperymentalnymi dla kilku różnych przypadków. Analiza wyników wyładowania iskrowego w polu prędkości potwierdza, że model prawidłowo przewiduje czas trwania wyładowania z wieloma przeskokami iskry, odkształcenie iskry podczas pierwszego przeskoku w danym wyładowaniu, napięcie i natężenie we wtórnym obwodzie układu zapłonowego oraz energię dostarczoną do łuku elektrycznego. Wyniki zapłonu i spalania w jednocylin-drowym silniku badawczym AVL pokazały natomiast, że pole prędkości powstałe w cylindrze podczas procesów wymiany ładunku i sprężania może znacznie odkształcić łuk elektryczny podczas zapłonu oraz wpłynąć na położenie pierwszego jądra płomienia. Wyniki numeryczne przebiegu ciśnienia w cylindrze oraz wydzielania ciepła są zgodne z danymi eksperymentalnymi, co potwierdza, że przedstawiony model poprawnie przewiduje proces zapłonu, podczas gdy model spalania prawidłowo opisuje propagację płomienia. Przedstawiony model został również użyty do obliczeń spalania w silniku badawczym o przeciwbieżnym ruchu tłoków PAMAR-4, w którym występują po dwie świece zapłonowe w każdej z komór spalania. Wyniki numeryczne przebiegu ciśnienia w cylindrze oraz wydzielania ciepła ponownie są zgodne z danymi eksperymentalnymi, co pokazuje, że przedstawiony model jest zdolny do obliczeń zapłonu z kilku świec w jednej komorze spalania, podczas gdy model spalania *G*-equation jest w stanie przewidzieć propagację odrębnych frontów płomienia pochodzących z różnych źródeł zapłonu.

Słowa kluczowe: zapłon iskrowy, modelowanie spalania, AVL FireTM, silniki tłokowe

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Approximately ninety percent of heat and electricity generated on earth is produced by combustion processes. Although the energy conversion methods which are alternative to combustion are of great interest, the vision of replacing combustion with these methods completely seems to be the far distant future. Therefore, besides promoting and developing new solutions for energy conversion which are not based on combustion, there is a strong need to make combustion processes cleaner and more efficient. This concerns all combustion-based power and energy systems such as industrial burners, gas turbines, furnaces and reciprocating engines in all applications, i.e. automotive, marine and power generation.

In piston engines combustion always takes place within a turbulent flow field. The reason of this is that the turbulence increases the mixing processes and thereby enhances combustion. Furthermore, turbulent combustion in Internal Combustion (IC) engines can be subdivided in terms of mixing into premixed, non-premixed and partially premixed combustion. For example, combustion in SI engines occurs under premixed conditions. In contrast, combustion in Compression-Ignition (CI) engines takes place under non-premixed or partially premixed conditions. These two different combustion modes require different control measures as well as different optimization methods.

In SI engines fuel and oxidizer are mixed in a turbulent manner for a sufficiently long time before the electrical spark ignites the mixture. The deposition of electrical energy from the spark ionizes the gas and heats it to several thousand Kelvins. Since this level of temperature is much too high to allow the species present in normal combustion products to exist, combustion reactions take place at the outer surface of the plasma

channel where the conditions are ideal for rapid chemical activity (temperatures of one thousand to a few thousand Kelvins) [1, 2]. These generate a flame kernel that grows at first by laminar, then by turbulent flame propagation. Usually, the consequent turbulent flame front travels through the combustion chamber until the whole mixture is burned. However, it is possible that a portion of the end-gas (mixture of fuel, air and residual gas) can spontaneously ignite ahead of the propagating flame. When this auto-ignition takes place, there is an extremely rapid release of chemical energy in the end-gas, causing very high local pressures and the propagation of pressure waves of substantial amplitude across the combustion chamber. These abnormal combustion phenomena, which are known as *Knock*, are of concern because they can lead to major engine damage.

The optimization of the combustion process in SI engines requires in-depth identification and understanding of all related phenomena such as mixture formation, spark ignition, turbulent flame propagation, flame quenching or knock. For many years numerical modeling has been used to support the development of IC engines, shorten the time span of the development process and minimize costs by eliminating the need of testing prototypes and conducting experimental investigations. Since Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) codes have become commonly used in commercial applications, the requirements for the predictive capabilities of the models have significantly increased. Thanks to the increase of computational performance of modern CPUs, the phenomena that previously have been described in a simplified manner can now be modeled with more detail.

Chapter 2

Motivation and objective

This thesis focuses on numerical description and modeling of the spark ignition process, which is crucial for the initiation of combustion and very early flame propagation in SI engines. The work is motivated by the literature review on both experimental and numerical investigations of the spark ignition which show that the complexity of this phenomenon makes its modeling a very challenging task. Although several ignition models for 3D CFD combustion simulations have been developed during the recent years, in each of them only particular aspects of the ignition process are accurately described while others are taken into account in a simplified manner, or even completely omitted. It proves that there is still space for improvements in spark ignition modeling and it is desirable to develop new ignition models for 3D CFD combustion modeling.

The objective of this work is to develop a predictive ignition model which provides for all aspects of the spark ignition that have influence on early flame kernel formation, growth and transition to the turbulent flame propagation. The proposed model builds upon several studies on the ignition process and integrates sub-models for the individual phenomena of the spark ignition. The sub-models for the electrical circuit of the ignition system, for the spark plasma dynamics, for the heat transfer from the spark towards surrounding mixture, for the ignition delay of the mixture and for the early flame kernel growth are coupled together to form one comprehensive ignition model. The model is implemented into the AVL FireTM CFD solver in the context of the G -equation combustion model [3]. By the use of CFD simulations it is possible to assess the gas exchange, combustion and wall heat losses in an IC engine. The proposed ignition model additionally allows to predict the temporal development and deflection of the spark-plasma channel,

the ignition delay time and the position of the initial flame kernel. In comparison to other approaches, a more detailed physical model is developed to accurately describe each phenomenon and gain a more complete understanding of the spark ignition process in SI engines.

The thesis is divided into seven chapters. After the introduction in Chapter 1 and motivation in Chapter 2, the theory of spark ignition process in SI engines and the literature review on the experimental investigations of the spark ignition are presented in Chapter 3. Chapter 4 discusses the theory of premixed turbulent combustion modeling in SI engines. The underlying differential equations for reacting flows are studied, both in the instantaneous and in the averaged form. As for the turbulence modeling, a statistical approach towards Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes equations (RANS) is presented and RANS-based combustion models for 3D CFD are reviewed. In Chapter 5 the ignition models for combustion initiation in CFD codes are reviewed with comments on the advantages, disadvantages and simplifications of each model. That is followed by Chapter 6 with a detailed description and methodology of implementation of a new ignition model into the AVL FireTM software. In Chapter 7 an extensive and thorough validation of the proposed model is performed. The simulation results are compared to available experimental data of the spark discharge process in a high-velocity flow field, measurement data from a single cylinder AVL research engine and measurement data from a 2-stroke Opposed-Piston (OP) research engine. In case of the engine simulations, results of the new model are additionally compared to the results without the ignition model to show the importance of a proper description of the ignition process and prove that not taking ignition phenomenon into account leads to a significant error. The summary and conclusions are the content of Chapter 8 which closes this work.

Chapter 3

Description of the Spark Ignition process

3.1 Ignition systems in Internal Combustion Engines

The primary purpose of the ignition system in IC engines is to initiate the flame propagation of the air-fuel mixture at the right timing of the engine cycle, in a repeatable cycle-by-cycle manner, and over the full load and speed range of the engine. During the spark discharge the electrical energy from the spark ionizes the gas and heats it to several thousand Kelvins forming a channel of a hot plasma. Since this level of temperature is much too high to allow the species present in normal combustion products to exist, combustion reactions take place at the outer surface of the plasma channel where the conditions are ideal for rapid chemical activity (temperatures of one thousand to a few thousand Kelvins) [1,2]. These generate a flame kernel that grows at first by laminar, then by turbulent flame propagation. The consequent turbulent flame front travels through the combustion chamber until the whole mixture is burned.

Historically, Mechanical Breaker Ignition (MBI) systems have been widely used to generate the spark discharge in SI engines. Although they have been replaced by more sophisticated ignition systems in modern engines, they provide a useful introduction to the ignition system design and operation. Figure 3.1 shows a simplified schematic of a typical MBI system which consists of two electrical circuits — the primary circuit and the secondary circuit. The primary circuit includes the battery, the primary inductance L_p , the primary resistance R_p and the switch. The secondary circuit includes the secondary

Figure 3.1: Simplified electrical scheme of the inductive system.

inductance L_s , the secondary resistance R_s , the total secondary capacitance C_s and the spark plug. When the switch is closed, the current starts to flow through the primary circuit and sets up the magnetic field within the iron of the ignition coil. The amount of energy stored in the primary circuit equals [2]:

$$E_p = \frac{1}{2} L_p i_p^2 \quad (3.1.1)$$

where the level of the current in the primary circuit is:

$$i_p(t) = \frac{V_p}{R_p} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{R_p}{L_p} \cdot t} \right) \quad (3.1.2)$$

with V_p being the supply voltage. The primary current requires time to build up, as shown in Fig. 3.2a. At low speeds the time of the switch making the contact is sufficient for the primary current to reach the maximum permitted by the resistance of the circuit. At high engine speeds, the term $1 - e^{-\frac{R_p}{L_p} \cdot t}$ becomes significant and the primary current may not reach its maximum. At the prescribed time of ignition, the switch opens the primary circuit and the primary current falls to zero. The resulting decay of the magnetic flux in the coil induces a high voltage in the secondary winding of the coil. If there is no spark discharge (there is no spark plug connected or the gap is too long, etc.), the voltage in the secondary circuit has a shape of a damped sinusoidal waveform as shown in Fig. 3.2b. The peak value of this voltage is the maximum voltage that can be provided by the ignition system and is called the available voltage V_a :

$$V_a = \left(\frac{2E_s}{C_s} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3.1.3)$$

where E_s is the energy available in the secondary winding of the coil. If all the energy stored in the primary winding of the coil is transferred to the secondary ($E_p = E_s$), then

$$V_a = i_p \left(\frac{L_p}{C_s} \right)^{1/2} \quad (3.1.4)$$

In case of a discharge, the voltage at the spark plug reaches the breakdown voltage V_{bd} and a spark is deposited between the electrodes. After the spark occurs, the voltage is reduced to a lower level until all energy E_s is dissipated and the spark disappears. The available voltage of the ignition system V_a must exceed the breakdown voltage V_{bd} to ensure the spark discharge. The following spark must possess sufficient energy and duration to initiate combustion under various operating conditions of an engine.

Figure 3.2: Current and voltage waveform for the breaker ignition system.

There are several shortcomings of the MBI systems. The major one is the decrease in the available voltage as engine speed increases due to limitation of the current switching capability of the mechanical breaker and the decrease in time available for building up the primary coil energy. Due to the high source impedance, the system is also sensitive to side-tracking across the spark plug insulator. Furthermore, the breaker points are subject to electrical and mechanical wear which requires short maintenance intervals. Thanks to the advancement in the semiconductor engineering, it was possible to overcome limitations of the MBI systems by replacing them with the solid state type ignition systems which use electronic devices (transistors, capacitors, diodes, etc.) to control the ignition system functions and the discharge timing. The ignition systems widely used nowadays can be divided by means of the type of the ignition energy storage in the primary circuit into:

- Transistorized Coil Ignition (TCI) systems which store the ignition energy in the magnetic field of the primary inductance of the ignition coil $E_p = L_p i_p^2 / 2$
- Capacitive Discharge Ignition (CDI) systems which store the ignition energy in the electrical field of the capacitor $E_p = C_p V_p^2 / 2$

Figure 3.3: Schematics of transistorized coil ignition (left) and capacitive-discharge ignition (right) systems.

Transistorized Coil Ignition

The TCI systems were developed to reduce the ignition system maintenance, extend the spark plug life and improve the ignition of lean and dilute mixtures. They are built with use of transistors (Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor, IGBT) which control the current flow in the primary circuit of the system. The role of the breaker (mechanical or electronic) is therefore reduced to the pulse generator which synchronizes the system with the rotational speed of an engine. In contrast to the MBI systems, the TCI systems are characterized by higher secondary voltage thanks to the pulse work of the transistor.

Capacitive Discharge Ignition

The CDI systems use a capacitor rather than an induction coil to store the ignition energy. The capacitance and the charging voltage of the capacitor determine the amount of the stored energy. The capacitor of $1 \div 2 \mu\text{F}$ is charged through the DC/DC converter up to $300 \div 500 \text{ V}$ which gives the stored energy of $50 \div 150 \text{ mJ}$. At the ignition timing, the impulse from the pulse generator triggers the thyristor (Silicon Controlled Rectifier, SCR) and the energy stored in the capacitor is discharged into the ignition coil or ignition transformer stepping up the primary voltage to 35 kV . This high voltage is discharged across the spark gap. The major advantage of the CDI system is that the capacitor can be fully charged in a very short time (typically 1 ms), which means that the CDI system

is suited to applications where an insufficient dwell time is available (such as high rpm engines or engines with multiple spark discharges per one cycle). The CDI systems have a fast voltage rise ($3 \div 10 \text{ kV}/\mu\text{s}$) compared to the TCI systems ($300 \div 500 \text{ V}/\mu\text{s}$) and a shorter spark duration ($50 \div 80 \mu\text{s}$) compared to the TCI systems (up to 2 ms).

3.2 Physics of the Spark Discharge

The purpose of this section is to provide a physical background to the spark discharge phenomenon. During the spark discharge process a high-temperature plasma channel (also called the spark channel within this thesis) is induced between the two electrodes. In order to achieve an electrical discharge at the gap of a spark plug, it is necessary to apply a sufficiently high voltage. The ignition systems used in SI engines to generate this voltage are described in section 3.1. The spark discharge in an engine takes place when the piston is close to the Top Dead Center (TDC) and triggers the chemical reactions in the surrounding mixture, which result in the formation of the flame kernels and the following flame propagation. According to Heywood [2] the spark discharge in SI engines can be divided into three characteristic phases: the breakdown phase, the arc phase and the glow phase. Each of these phases is characterized by a different duration and a different levels of the voltage and current in the secondary circuit of the ignition system. The differences between the breakdown, the arc and the glow phase finally lead to a different energy amount transferred to the surrounding mixture. The temporal history of the voltage and current for a conventional ignition coil together with a typical energy amount supplied to the air-fuel mixture is given in Fig. 3.4. The theoretical description of the spark discharge also includes the ionization processes which lead to the establishment of the conductive plasma channel between the ground and the center electrode of the spark plug [4,5]. These happen during the initial rise of the voltage and current in the secondary circuit of the ignition system and can be considered as a pre-breakdown phase of the spark discharge.

Pre-breakdown phase

In typical ignition systems it takes up to several microseconds to rise the voltage to the breakdown voltage V_{bd} sufficient for an electrical discharge. The level of the breakdown voltage V_{bd} is influenced by the shape of the electrode, the gap size, the gas composition and pressure, as well as the presence of the ionization process [4]. It is usually calculated

Figure 3.4: Temporal history of the current and the voltage during the breakdown, arc and glow phases for a convention coil ignition system [2].

with the Paschen's law [6], which implies that V_{bd} only depends on the pressure p and the electrode gap d

$$V_{bd} = \frac{B \cdot p \cdot d}{\ln \frac{A \cdot p \cdot d}{k}} \quad (3.2.1)$$

where k represents a constant for the conditions in the streamer breakdown and A as well as B are experimentally determined constants for the material of the electrodes and the gas.

The process of the formation of the spark channel is explained in Fig. 3.5. The electrical field between the spark electrodes induced by the applied voltage accelerates free electrons originating from thermal or photo ionization, which ionize other gas molecules by a collision (A and B in Fig. 3.5). In this process, an electron is split from the gas molecule so that a positive ion and a free electron remain. The accelerated electron induces further collisions constantly providing and consuming free electrons, thus increasing the density of electrons available in the gas. All free electrons in the reservoir are accelerated by the

electrical field towards the anode, colliding with gas molecules on their way. This causes an electronic avalanche, which can merge and build a low conductive streamer (C and D in Fig. 3.5). As soon as the streamer reaches the anode, a high conductive plasma channel is established, starting the breakdown phase.

Figure 3.5: Discharge process with electronic avalanche [5].

Breakdown phase

As soon as the breakdown voltage V_{bd} is reached between the electrodes and a high conductive plasma is formed, the current through the gap increases drastically (up to 100–200 A), discharging the capacity close to the spark gap C_s . As a result the voltage across the gap drops to a few percent of the V_{bd} . The amount of energy released during the breakdown phase can be calculated as the difference in electrostatic field energies before and after the breakdown, expressed in terms of the voltage before and after the breakdown and the capacity of the spark plug C_s . Usually, the voltage after the breakdown is neglected and the energy equals

$$E_{bd} = \frac{C_s \cdot V_{bd}^2}{2} \quad (3.2.2)$$

The diameter of the spark channel formed during the breakdown depends on the electrical energy in this phase. Under engine operating conditions the initial diameter of the plasma channel is approximately $50 \mu\text{m}$ [2, 7–9]. The energy released during the breakdown is transferred to the plasma column almost without losses. The temperature

and pressure in the column rise rapidly to values of up to 60000 K and 100 bar [2, 4]. As a consequence, the plasma starts to expand and a shock wave is emitted at supersonic speed. As the pressure wave separates from the channel, the plasma temperatures fall below 10000 K. The breakdown phase reaches a very high power level (~ 1 MW), but it lasts only about 10 ns and the absolute amount of energy transferred to the surrounding gas during this phase is low (0.3 – 1 mJ according to Heywood [2]) comparing to the arc and glow phases. The energy transport is controlled mainly by a convective transport, while in the subsequent arc and glow phases a heat conduction into the surrounding mixture becomes more important.

Arc phase

The arc phase follows the breakdown phase during the spark discharge. It is characterized by a low voltage along the plasma channel (< 100 V) and the current as high as the external circuit permits [2]. The level of gas ionization is low (about 1%) and the voltage drop at the electrodes is a significant fraction of the arc voltage. The gas temperature in the arc is limited to about 6000 K due to the heat conduction. The arc requires a hot cathode spot, which causes an evaporation of the cathode material and increased heat losses into the cathode. Finally, only up to 50% of the released energy is transferred to the surrounding gas [2]. A low power level of the arc phase, short duration (~ 10 μ s) and significant heat losses to the electrodes contribute to only about 1 mJ of the energy transferred to the gas during this phase, similarly as during the breakdown phase.

Glow phase

With decrease of the available energy and drop of the current in the secondary circuit, a transition from the arc to the glow phase occurs. In Heywood [2] a value of 100 mA is given as an arc/glow transition threshold. The glow phase is characterized by currents less than 100 mA decreasing with the energy available in the secondary circuit. The voltage at the spark gap may reach over 1 kV depending on the conditions. Typically, a large voltage drop at the cathode (300 – 500 V) and low ionization levels ($< 1\%$) are observed. Energy losses are even higher than during the arc phase and peak plasma channel temperatures are about 3000 K [2]. The power level of the glow phase is low (~ 50 W) but its duration is long (up to 2 ms) comparing to the breakdown and arc phases. Therefore, most of the electrical energy from the ignition system is supplied to the spark channel during the

glow phase (up to 100 mJ at a single discharge event in modern ignition systems). Due to the long burning time, the glow discharge is also very sensitive to the flow field which can transport the plasma away from the electrodes. The deflection and elongation of the spark leads to an increased voltage needed to sustain the plasma channel. Maly [1] states that for flow velocities up to 15 m/s the discharge generates enough new electrons and ions to follow the increase in channel length smoothly and the spark voltage increases accordingly. For higher velocities, the spark channel may reach such a length that the plasma column voltage rises above the value required for generating a new spark directly across the electrodes. An interruption of the old spark and a deposition of a new one before the energy in the coil has been consumed is called the *restrike*. The breakdown voltage of the restrike is much lower than the breakdown voltage of the initial spark formation, since sufficient initial electrons and ions are already available at the cathode. In case of multiple restrikes, the individual channels are separated from each other and contain only fractions of the total electrical energy. With lengthening of the spark by the flow, the ratio of the plasma voltage to anode and cathode falls rises considerably and the heat losses due to the heat conduction to the electrodes drop. Additionally, the increase in plasma column voltage may conveniently be used to measure the flow field properties under real engine conditions [1].

3.3 Inflammation by the Spark Discharge

To ignite the mixture with the spark discharge, the energy released by the discharge must be locally sufficient to overcome the activation energy of the exoenergetic reactions. As described in the previous section, the plasma channel established between the spark electrodes during the breakdown phase contains considerable concentrations of ionized, dissociated and excited species at temperatures up to 60000 K. With the following arc and glow phases, a continuous heat source to the center of the spark channel is provided, keeping up the high temperatures of the plasma. The temperature of several thousand Kelvins in the center of the arc and glow channel is too high for stable molecules to exist, while outside of the channel, ambient temperatures prevail. The extremely high temperature gradients at the plasma surface imply considerable gradients in concentrations of radicals such as H and O, known to participate in chain branching reactions important for

the flame initiation [1]. The increased concentrations of H and O radicals combined with the fairly suitable temperatures for the formation of stable molecules lead to acceleration of the exoenergetic reactions. As a result, irrespective of the interior conditions of the plasma, combustion reactions take place at the outer plasma surface where the conditions are ideal for rapid chemical activity [2]. Following these facts, the ignition takes place at the spark plasma surface where the first flame kernel develops, giving a start for the flame propagation, firstly in a laminar, then in a turbulent manner.

3.4 Experimental investigations of the Spark Ignition

Understanding of the spark ignition process is important for the improvement of fuel efficiency and reduction of emissions of SI engines. A number of experimental investigations on the spark discharge and flame kernel initiation has been carried out over the last several decades. Since the ignition process by the spark discharge is a complex phenomenon, each study is devoted to a particular aspect of the spark ignition (e.g. characteristics of the ignition systems, energy transfer through the spark channel, formation of the flame kernel). The most important studies which contributed to the understanding of the ignition process and allowed for the development of numerical models are reviewed in this section.

Kim and Anderson [10] investigated a rapid method of obtaining the convection velocity of the bulk gas near the spark plug gap of a firing engine at the time of ignition. With the detailed measurements of the ignition system, authors were able to propose a model for the gas column voltage during the arc and glow phases of the spark discharge. The provided model was later used by other researchers to estimate the energy supplied to the spark channel in ignition modeling [11]. Paschley et al. [12] also performed detailed experimental investigations of a typical TCI ignition system with a forced velocity field at the spark gap. They distinguished different phases of the spark discharge and proposed models for the breakdown voltage and gas column voltage of the spark channel. Verhoeven [13] used the technique based on holographic interferometry to measure the total energy transferred from the spark to the surrounding gases for a number of spark plug electrode geometries, flow velocities, gas pressures and coil charge times. With these measurements he estimated the efficiency of the heat transfer from the spark to

the surrounding gases for the arc and glow discharge modes. Sher et al. [14] performed a fundamental study of the spark formation in air and proposed a model to calculate the spark temperature after the breakdown. They concluded that the temperature of the spark channel drops rapidly from a very high initial value due to the heat dissipation and beyond a specific limit, the energy of the spark affects only the initial flame kernel radius, and not the temperature.

More complex studies consider the inflammation of the air-fuel mixtures by the spark discharge. In [15] Maly and Vogel studied the inflammation of methane-air mixtures at 4 bar and determined that the breakdown process of the spark discharge has the most influence on the radius of the forming kernel. Increasing the energy input during the arc phase in CDI also has an effect on the activated volume, while during the glow phase little, if any of the additional energy reaches the inflammation zone. Ziegler et al. [16] also performed an experimental study of the formation of lean methane-air flames and demonstrated that the shock wave separates from the spark kernel after the breakdown and flame initiation is detectable 1 ms after the breakdown, during the arc or the glow phase. Kravchik et al. [17, 18] applied the model proposed in [14] to study the ignition of methane-air mixtures. They showed that the spark development into combustion can be described as a two-step process. Firstly, the spark plasma expands with a pressure wave after the breakdown. This is followed by a longer period, in which energy and mass are transferred by conduction and diffusion. The initial flame kernel is formed during the second stage, at the spark channel surface. Thiele et al. [19] conducted experimental investigations of the spark ignition of an initially quiescent hydrogen-air mixtures. They also proposed a 2D model which predicts the spark behavior for the phases subsequent to the breakdown using the Maxwell equations for quasi-stationary conditions for the electric field. The results showed that the pronounced heat losses to the electrode material have an effect on the shape of the early flame front. Results from experiments and simulations suggest the birth of a self-sustaining flame propagation for process times between 50 to 70 μs after the breakdown. Eisazadeh-Far [20] studied the flame kernel formation and propagation in premixed gases experimentally and theoretically. They concluded that major part of the discharge energy is dissipated by the cathode fall energy losses with only about 10 – 25% converted to thermal energy. Also increase in the heat capacity at

high temperatures is an important factor in dynamics and temperature rise in the spark channel.

There are several studies which focus on the ignitability of air-fuel mixtures under engine operating conditions. For example Fansler et al. [21] in a review on combustion instabilities in SI engines analyze the importance of the spark ignition process. They state that in modern Direct-Injection Spark-Ignition (DISI) engines the close coupling between injection and ignition produces high velocities and intense turbulence at the spark gap. Consequently, the shape of the spark, ignition kernels and the growing flame are subjected to deformations due to varying velocity fields. Suzuki et al. [22] performed optical engine experiments and pointed out that intensification of the turbulence in SI engines is closely related to the increased tumble ratio and strong flow fields which can blow-off the spark discharge and cause misfire. They found out that intensifying the discharge current prevents the spark blow-off and improves the ignition process. Wang et al. [23] also performed optical engine measurement to investigate the influence of the tumble generated in the combustion chamber on the ignition process and the initial flame propagation in modern DISI engines. They found out that the velocity at the spark gap can reach over 15 m/s and the spark channel can become significantly distorted during the spark discharge process with several restrikes possible. Dahms et al. [24] used Mie scattering and PIV measurements to study the spark ignition in a DISI engine and show that the high velocity flow near the spark gap interacts strongly with the spark discharge. They measured that the spark channel can stretch up to ~ 10 mm which leads to an increased instantaneous spark voltage and multiple restrikes back to the electrode gap. They have also captured the ignition point at a distinct location along the deflected spark channel.

Chapter 4

Combustion modeling in SI engines

In most technical applications, such as flow around a plane wing or a turbine blade, flow through a fuel injector or combustion in IC engines the flow field is characterized by a turbulent manner. In turbulent flows the mechanical properties of the fluid are subjected to quasi-random, time-dependent and three-dimensional variations over a wide range of time and length scales. The turbulent combustion forms an important subset of turbulent flows and its reacting nature imposes additional challenges of resolution of all relevant scales that govern turbulent reacting flows. The numerical modeling of turbulent combustion problems is based on the solution of a set of conservation equations for momentum and scalars, plus additional auxiliary equations which have very well-defined foundations in their instantaneous and spatially-resolved forms. Bilger et al. [25] have discussed various paradigms that have evolved over the years to address the turbulent combustion problems. The main challenge in practical solutions of the turbulent combustion is the separation of scales to overcome the coupled multiscale complexity of turbulent reacting flows. The significant progress that has been made in numerical solutions for a large class of problems enabled the use of computational fluid dynamics for the prediction and design of combustion in practical devices. This chapter reviews the governing equations of reacting flows and presents them in the context of Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS). The state-of-the-art models for the premixed turbulent combustion are also briefly described. The scope of this chapter is limited to premixed turbulent combustion modeling in RANS simulations, since the spark ignition model proposed in this work is implemented and integrated with the G -equation combustion model in the RANS context.

4.1 Conservation equations of reacting flows

Combustion involves multiple species reacting through multiple chemical reactions. The basic set of equations for reacting flows comprises the classical Navier-Stokes, species and energy transport equations. Following [26] the differences between these equations and the usual Navier-Stokes equations for non-reacting cases are:

- a reacting gas is a non-isothermal mixture of multiple species which must be tracked individually,
- species react chemically and the rate at which these reactions take place requires specific modeling,
- since the gas is a mixture of different species, the transport coefficients (heat diffusivity, species diffusion, viscosity, etc.) require specific attention.

In order to apply the Navier-Stokes equations for a multi-species, multi-reaction gas they require some additional terms. Firstly, species are characterized through their mass fractions Y_k or mole fractions X_k for $k = 1$ to N where N is the number of species in the reacting mixture. The mass fractions Y_k and the mole fractions X_k are defined by:

$$Y_k = \frac{m_k}{m}; \quad X_k = \frac{W}{W_k} Y_k \quad (4.1.1)$$

where m_k is the mass of species k , m is the total mass of gas in a given volume and W is the mean molecular weight of the mixture given by:

$$\frac{1}{W} = \sum_{k=1}^N \frac{Y_k}{W_k} \quad (4.1.2)$$

with molecular weight of the species k given by W_k .

Thermochemistry

For a mixture of N perfect gases the pressure p and density ρ are determined by:

$$p = \sum_{k=1}^N p_k; \quad \rho = \sum_{k=1}^N \rho_k \quad (4.1.3)$$

where partial pressure p_k is related to the temperature and density as:

$$p_k = \rho_k \frac{R}{W_k} T \quad (4.1.4)$$

where T is the temperature, R is the perfect gas constant and $\rho_k = \rho Y_k$. This leads to the well-known equation of state for a mixture of N perfect gases:

$$p = \rho \frac{R}{W} T \quad (4.1.5)$$

The enthalpy of a mixture is defined by the sum of the enthalpy of the single species, multiplied by their mass fraction:

$$h = \sum_{k=1}^N h_k Y_k \quad (4.1.6)$$

where the enthalpy of species k can be described as:

$$h_k = \int_{T_0}^T c_{pk} dT + \delta h_{f,k}^o \quad (4.1.7)$$

The mass enthalpy of formation of species k at temperature T_0 is denoted as $\delta h_{f,k}^o$. Usually the standard reference state used to tabulate formation enthalpies and reference temperature is $T_0 = 298.15$ K. With the specific heat capacity of the mixture at constant pressure c_p given by:

$$c_p = \sum_{k=1}^N c_{pk} Y_k \quad (4.1.8)$$

the enthalpy equation for a reacting mixture is as follows:

$$h = \int_{T_0}^T c_p dT + \sum_{k=1}^N h_{f,k}^o Y_k \quad (4.1.9)$$

Chemical kinetics

The chemical reactions during the combustion process are described by a large number of single reaction processes. The overall reaction rate and composition of the reacting mixture can be described by a chemical reaction mechanism. For a reaction mechanism

with N species and M reactions, the reaction processes are described by:

$$\sum_{k=1}^N \nu_{kj}^f \mathcal{M}_k \rightleftharpoons \sum_{k=1}^N \nu_{kj}^r \mathcal{M}_k \quad \text{for } j = 1, M \quad (4.1.10)$$

In this equation \mathcal{M}_k is the symbol for species k and the forward and reverse molar stoichiometric coefficients are denoted by ν^f and ν^r , respectively. The reaction rate of all forward and reverse reactions is as follows:

$$\omega_j = k_{fj} \prod_{k=1}^N [X_k]^{\nu_{kj}^f} - k_{rj} \prod_{k=1}^N [X_k]^{\nu_{kj}^r} \quad (4.1.11)$$

where $[X_k]$ represents the molar concentration of species k , while k_{fj} and k_{rj} describe the forward and reverse coefficients of reaction j . The reaction rate coefficients constitute a central problem of combustion modeling and they are usually modeled by the Arrhenius equation:

$$k_j = A_j T^{\beta_j} \exp\left(-\frac{E_j}{RT}\right) \quad (4.1.12)$$

To calculate the reaction rate for each reaction j , the activation energy E_j , the temperature exponent β_j and the frequency factor A_j need to be provided in the reaction mechanism. Finally, the chemical source term $\dot{\omega}_K$ is given by:

$$\dot{\omega}_k = W_k \sum_{j=1}^M \nu_{kj} \omega_j \quad \text{with } \nu_{kj} = \nu_{kj}^r - \nu_{kj}^f \quad (4.1.13)$$

Stoichiometry

In order to describe the mixture composition in premixed flames, a scalar ϕ is introduced. The equivalence ratio ϕ defines the ratio of the fuel mass fraction Y_F and the oxidizer mass fraction Y_O normalized by their stoichiometric ratio:

$$\phi = \frac{(Y_F/Y_O)}{(Y_F/Y_O)_{st}} \quad (4.1.14)$$

Considering this definition, $\phi > 1$ describes the mixture where the fuel is in excess and $\phi < 1$ describes the mixture where the oxidizer is in excess.

Conservation of momentum

The equation of momentum is the same in reacting and non-reacting flow:

$$\frac{\partial \rho u_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j u_i}{\partial x_j} = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \tau_{ij}}{\partial x_j} + F_i \quad (4.1.15)$$

where F_i is the body force, p is the static pressure and τ_{ij} is the viscous stress tensor which can be defined as:

$$\tau_{ij} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial u_j}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{2}{3} \mu \delta_{ij} \left(\frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_k} \right) \quad (4.1.16)$$

with δ_{ij} representing the Kronecker symbol and μ being the temperature-dependent viscosity. Even though this equation does not include explicit reaction terms, the flow is modified by combustion via the dynamic viscosity μ and density ρ which strongly change with temperature.

Conservation of mass and species

The total mass conservation equation is the same as for non-reactive flows, because combustion does not generate or consume total mass:

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (4.1.17)$$

The mass conservation for species k is as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \rho Y_k}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_i Y_k}{\partial x_i} = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}_j^k}{\partial x_j} + \dot{\omega}_k \quad \text{for } k = 1, N \quad (4.1.18)$$

where \mathcal{J}_i^k is the molecular diffusive flux of species k and $\dot{\omega}_k$ its reaction rate per unit volume. The molecular transport processes that cause the diffusive fluxes are quite complicated. The full equations and approximations for the diffusion velocities are given in [26].

Conservation of energy

It is possible to write multiple forms of energy conservation equation. The derivation and summary of different forms of conservation equations for energy and enthalpy are given in [26]. The conservation equation for the total enthalpy $h_t = h + u_i u_i / 2$ can be

written as follows:

$$\frac{\partial \rho h_t}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_j h_t}{\partial x_j} = \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\mathcal{J}_j^h + u_i \tau_{ij} \right) + u_j F_j \quad (4.1.19)$$

where $u_i \tau_{ij}$ is the power produced due to viscous forces and $u_j F_j$ is the power produced due to body forces.

Species molecular diffusivities are generally described using the Fick's law as follows:

$$\mathcal{J}_j^k = - \frac{\mu}{Sc_k} \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial x_j} \quad (4.1.20)$$

where Sc_k is the Schmidt number of the species k , defined as:

$$Sc_k = \frac{\mu}{\rho D_k} \quad (4.1.21)$$

and D_k is the molar diffusivity of the species k relative to the major species. More complex expressions can be used to describe multi-species molecular diffusion including Soret effects. However, species diffusion under temperature gradients and molecular transport due to pressure gradients are usually neglected.

Enthalpy diffusion can be described according to the Fourier law:

$$\mathcal{J}_j^h = - \frac{\mu}{Pr} \left[\frac{\partial h}{\partial x_j} + \sum_{k=1}^N \left(\frac{Pr}{Sc_k} - 1 \right) h_k \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial x_j} \right] \quad (4.1.22)$$

where the Prandtl number Pr compares the diffusive transport of momentum (viscous forces) and temperature. It can be written as a function of the thermal diffusivity λ and the constant pressure specific heat c_p :

$$Pr = \frac{\mu c_p}{\lambda} \quad (4.1.23)$$

4.2 Averaging of conservation equations

The full numerical simulation of described conservation equations is limited to very simple cases with low number of time and length scales present in the flow. The full solution in this kind of cases is obtained by means of Direct Numerical Simulations (DNS). In order to overcome the difficulties with the direct solution, an averaging of the conservation

equations is introduced to describe only the mean flow field. As a result, local fluctuation and turbulent structures are integrated in mean quantities and these structures are no longer described in simulation. During the averaging, each quantity f is split into a mean \bar{f} and a fluctuating component f' :

$$f = \bar{f} + f' \quad \text{with} \quad \overline{f'} = 0 \quad (4.2.1)$$

This averaging technique is widely used in the non-reacting fluid mechanics but introduces unclosed correlations that need to be modeled. The numerical procedure is called Reynolds Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) modeling. In the turbulent flames, fluctuations of density are observed because of the thermal heat release. Reynolds averaging of the mass balance leads to:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\overline{\rho u_i} + \overline{\rho' u'_i}) = 0 \quad (4.2.2)$$

where the unclosed correlation between the density and the velocity fluctuation appears $\overline{\rho' u'_i}$ and requires modeling. The Reynolds averaging for variable density flows introduces many other unclosed correlations between any quantity f and density fluctuations $\overline{\rho' f'}$. To avoid this difficulty, mass-weighted averages (called Favre averages) are usually preferred:

$$f = \tilde{f} + f'' \quad \text{with} \quad \tilde{f} = \frac{\overline{\rho f}}{\bar{\rho}} \quad \text{and} \quad \overline{f''} = 0 \quad (4.2.3)$$

Favre averaging of instantaneous conservation equations yields:

Conservation of mass

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j}{\partial x_j} = 0 \quad (4.2.4)$$

Conservation of momentum

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_i}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j \tilde{u}_i}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial \overline{\rho u'_j u'_i}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial x_i} + \frac{\partial \overline{\tau_{ij}}}{\partial x_j} + \bar{F}_i \quad (4.2.5)$$

Conservation of species

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{Y}_k}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j \tilde{Y}_k}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial \overline{\rho u_j'' Y_k''}}{\partial x_j} - \frac{\partial \overline{\mathcal{J}_j^k}}{\partial x_j} + \bar{\dot{\omega}}_k \quad (4.2.6)$$

Conservation of enthalpy

$$\frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{h}_t}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_j \tilde{h}_t}{\partial x_j} = - \frac{\partial \overline{\rho u_j'' h_t''}}{\partial x_j} + \frac{\partial \bar{p}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\overline{\mathcal{J}_j^h} + \overline{u_i \tau_{ij}} \right) + \overline{u_j F_j} \quad (4.2.7)$$

The objective of the turbulent combustion modeling is to propose closures for the unknown quantities appearing in averaged conservation equations, namely:

Reynolds stresses $(\overline{u_i'' u_j''})$

An approximation of the Reynolds stress term is provided by the turbulence model. Combustion models are usually based on turbulence modeling developed for non-reactive flows (e.g. $k-\varepsilon$) rewritten in terms of Favre averaging. Heat release effects on the Reynolds stresses are generally not explicitly taken into account.

Species and enthalpy turbulent fluxes $(\overline{u_i'' Y_k''})$ and $(\overline{u_i'' h'' s})$

These fluxes are generally closed using a classical gradient assumption:

$$\overline{\rho u_j'' Y_k''} = - \frac{\mu_t}{Sc_{kt}} \frac{\partial \tilde{Y}_k}{\partial x_j} \quad (4.2.8)$$

where μ_t is the turbulent velocity estimated from the turbulence model and Sc_{kt} is a turbulent Schmidt number for species k .

Laminar diffusive fluxes $(\overline{\mathcal{J}_j^k}, \overline{\mathcal{J}_j^h})$

These fluxes are usually small compared to turbulent transport and can be neglected assuming large turbulence level.

Species chemical reaction rates $\dot{\omega}_k$

Modeling these mean reaction rates is the objective of most studies on the turbulent flames. Some of the correlations used in turbulent combustion models are described in section 4.5.

4.3 Principles of premixed combustion modeling

The structure of a laminar premixed flame is shown in Fig. 4.1. Fresh mixture (fuel and oxidizer) and burnt gases (combustion products) are separated by a thin reaction zone and strong temperature gradient with typical ratios between burnt and fresh gases of about 5–7. A premixed laminar flame propagates towards fresh gases. Because of the thermal fluxes corresponding to the temperature gradient, fresh gases are preheated and start to burn. The local imbalance between heat diffusion and chemical consumption leads to the propagation of the laminar flame front with speed s_L , that depends on the mixture physical and chemical properties.

For a simple on-step irreversible chemical scheme where reactants are converted into products, the flame is described using a progress variable c , such as $c = 0$ in the fresh gases and $c = 1$ in the fully burnt state. The progress variable may be defined as a reduced temperature or a reduced mass fraction as:

$$c = \frac{T - T_u}{T_b - T_u} \quad \text{or} \quad c = \frac{Y_F - Y_F^u}{Y_F^b - Y_F^u} \quad (4.3.1)$$

where T , T_u and T_b are the local, the unburnt and the burnt temperatures respectively, while Y_F , Y_F^u and Y_F^b are the local, the unburnt and the burnt gas fuel mass fractions. Y_F^b is non-zero for fuel rich mixture. For the same molecular and thermal diffusivities (unity Lewis number) and adiabatic combustion, the two definitions of c are equivalent and mass and energy balance equations are reduced to a single balance equation for the progress variable:

$$\frac{\partial \rho c}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \rho u_i c}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\rho D_c \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_i} + \dot{\omega} \right) \quad (4.3.2)$$

where $\dot{\omega}$ is the chemical production rate of c (reaction rate) and ρD_c is the molecular diffusivity of c .

Figure 4.1: Structure of a laminar premixed flame [27].

For RANS, the Favre-averaged reaction progress variable transport equation is:

$$\frac{\partial \bar{x}\tilde{c}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \overline{\rho\tilde{u}_k\tilde{c}}}{\partial x_k} = \bar{\omega}_c + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \left(\overline{\rho D_c \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_k}} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \overline{\rho u_k'' c''} \quad (4.3.3)$$

Averaging the progress variable transport equation results in additional unclosed terms that require modeling. These terms are the molecular transport term and the Reynolds flux. The simplest closure model for the molecular transport term is based on the assumption that the mass diffusivity ρD_c is uncorrelated with reaction progress variable:

$$\left(\overline{\rho D_c \frac{\partial c}{\partial x_k}} \right) = \overline{\rho D_c} \frac{\partial \tilde{c}}{\partial x_k} \quad (4.3.4)$$

in which an additional assumption has been made to allow for the replacement of the filtered value \bar{c} with the Favre-filtered value \tilde{c} inside the spatial derivative. In reality, the mass diffusivity ρD_c is often a function of c , but more complicated modeling is rarely justified in a view of more pressing modeling issues associated with other terms in the transport equation.

In a turbulent premixed flame, fluctuations in the instantaneous velocity and reaction progress variable will occur due to the turbulence. The heat release ensures that an upward (or a downward) fluctuation in c will be associated with an upward (or a downward)

fluctuation in u . Thus, the physics ensures that u and c are statistically correlated. For this situation the standard gradient model for turbulent scalar transport may be written as:

$$\overline{\rho u_k'' c''} = -\bar{\rho} D_T \frac{\partial \tilde{c}}{\partial x_k} \quad (4.3.5)$$

where D_T is a turbulent diffusivity. A difficulty arises at once, since the gradient model predicts a negative value of the Reynolds flux when the mean progress variable gradient is positive and vice versa. Thus, the standard gradient transport model is not valid in general for turbulent premixed flames. The countergradient transport can be only resolved with solving separate balance equations for each component of Reynolds stress $\overline{\rho u_i'' u_j''}$ and Reynolds flux $\overline{\rho u_i'' c''}$. The Bray-Moss-Libby (BML) model [28] remains one of the most successful closure approaches in this regard.

4.4 Regimes of turbulent premixed combustion

As the mean burning rate $\bar{\omega}$ cannot be obtained from an averaging of Arrhenius law, a physical approach is required to derive models for turbulent combustion. Firstly, it is necessary to identify premixed turbulent combustion regimes by comparing turbulence and chemical characteristic length and time scales. This analysis leads to combustion diagrams which are helpful to select and develop the relevant combustion model for given conditions.

The regimes of premixed turbulent combustion can be plotted on the well-known Borghi diagram [29] later modified by Peters [3]. For turbulent premixed flames, the turbulence is represented by the velocity fluctuation magnitude u' together with the integral length scale l_t , while the thermochemistry is represented by the laminar flame thickness δ_l and the laminar burning velocity s_L . With turbulent integral length scale characteristics estimated as $\tau_t = l_t/u'$, the Reynolds number is:

$$Re = \frac{u' l_t}{\nu} = \frac{u'}{s_L} \frac{l_t}{\delta_l} \quad (4.4.1)$$

Defining the chemical time scale τ_c as the ratio of δ_l and s_L the Damköhler number becomes:

$$Da = \frac{\tau_t}{\tau_c} = \frac{l_t s_L}{\delta_l u'} \quad (4.4.2)$$

The Karlovitz number Ka corresponds to the smallest eddies (Kolmogorov) and is the ratio of the chemical time scale τ_c to the Kolmogorov time τ_k :

$$Ka = \frac{\tau_c}{\tau_k} = \frac{\delta_l u_k}{l_k s_L} \quad (4.4.3)$$

The size l_k and the velocity u_k of Kolmogorov structures are:

$$l_k = \left(\frac{\nu^3}{\varepsilon} \right)^{1/4}; \quad u_k = (\nu\varepsilon)^{1/4} \quad (4.4.4)$$

where ε is the dissipation of the turbulent kinetic energy k . With integral length scale l_t :

$$l_t = \left(\frac{u'^3}{\varepsilon} \right) \quad (4.4.5)$$

and using $\nu = \delta_l s_L$, corresponding to a unity flame Reynolds number gives:

$$Ka = \left(\frac{u'}{s_L} \right)^{3/2} \left(\frac{l_t}{\delta_l} \right)^{-1/2} \quad (4.4.6)$$

Reynolds, Damköhler and Karlovitz numbers are related as:

$$Re = Da^2 Ka^2 \quad (4.4.7)$$

The Karlovitz number also compares the flame and the Kolmogorov lengths scales:

$$Ka = \left(\frac{\delta_l}{l_k} \right)^2 \quad (4.4.8)$$

When $\delta_l > l_k$, Kolmogorov scales are able to enter and thicken the flame preheat zone. When $\delta_r > l_k$, Kolmogorov scales are able to enter and break the reaction zone, which

corresponds to the transition value of the Karlovitz number, Ka_δ for $\delta_r = l_k$:

$$Ka_\delta = \left(\frac{\delta_r}{l_k}\right)^2 = \left(\frac{\delta_r}{\delta_l}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\delta_l}{l_k}\right)^2 \quad (4.4.9)$$

For most premixed flames, $\delta_r/\delta_l \approx 1/10$, corresponding to a transition for $Ka = 100$ ($Ka_\delta = 1$).

Figure 4.2: Regime diagram for turbulent premixed combustion [3].

The regimes of premixed turbulent combustion can be plotted on the Peters-Borghgi diagram [30] using the length scale (l_t/δ_l) and the velocity (u'/s_L) ratio (Fig. 4.2). The following regimes can be identified:

- $Ka < 1$: *Flamelet regime* with two subdivisions depending on the velocity ratio u'/s_L
 - *Wrinkled flamelet* for $u'/s_L < 1$. Since u' can be considered as the rotation speed of the large turbulent motions, turbulent structures cannot wrinkle the flame surface and interact with the flame front. The laminar propagation is dominant and turbulence-combustion interaction is limited.
 - *Corrugated flamelet* for $u'/s_L > 1$. In this case large turbulent structures become larger than the laminar flame speed and start to wrinkle the flame front leading to the formation of pockets of the fresh and burnt gases.

- $1 < Ka \leq 100$ ($Ka_\delta < 1$): *Thin reaction zone*. In this regime turbulent motions affect and thicken the flame preheat zone. Simultaneously, they still cannot modify the reaction zone which remains thin and close to a laminar reaction zone.
- $Ka > 100$ ($Ka_\delta > 1$): *Broken reaction zone*. In this case both diffusion and reaction zones are affected by turbulent motions. Laminar structure could be no longer identified.

4.5 RANS combustion models for premixed turbulent flame propagation

A proper description of the reaction rate closures for turbulent combustion has to be developed from physical analysis. According to [27], most combustion models are derived from one of the three approaches illustrated in Fig. 4.3.

Turbulent mixing

One of the common assumptions in turbulent combustion modeling is that chemical time scales are shorter than turbulent time scales (large Damköhler numbers). In that case the reaction rate is limited by turbulent mixing expressed in terms of scalar dissipation rates. The small scale dissipation rate of species controls the mixing of the reactants and plays a dominant role, even for finite rate chemistry.

Geometrical analysis

In the geometrical analysis the flame front is a geometrical surface evolving in the turbulent flow field and linked to the instantaneous iso-surface of a mass or mixture fraction. In this situation, the flame is considered as an interface between fresh and burnt gases in premixed combustion. Geometrical analysis is usually related to the assumption that the flame is thin compared to the flow scales and each flame element behaves as a laminar flame (flamelet assumption). In this situation, mean reaction rates are estimated as the product of the available flame area per unit volume (the so-called flame surface density) and the mean reaction rate per unit of the flame area.

One-point statistics

This approach does not require assumptions on the flame structure. Mean reaction rates are expressed combining instantaneous reaction rates from Arrhenius equation with the joint probability density function leading to PDF modeling.

Figure 4.3: Modeling approaches for turbulent combustion [26].

4.5.1 Eddy Break-Up model

The Eddy Break-Up (EBU) model, firstly proposed by Spalding [31], is based on a phenomenological analysis of turbulent combustion assuming high Reynolds ($Re \gg 1$) and Damköhler ($Da \gg 1$) numbers. It represents the turbulent mixing approach. The underlying concept is that chemistry is fast and the mean reaction rate is mainly controlled by the turbulent mixing time τ_t and progress variable fluctuations:

$$\bar{\omega} = C_{EBU} \bar{\rho} \frac{\sqrt{\widetilde{c''^2}}}{\tau_t} \quad (4.5.1)$$

where the turbulent mixing time τ_t is estimated from the turbulence kinetic energy k and its dissipation rate ε according to:

$$\tau_t = \frac{k}{\varepsilon} \quad (4.5.2)$$

The progress variable fluctuations \widetilde{c}''^2 can be estimated based on the assumption of an infinitely thin flame front as:

$$\overline{\rho \widetilde{c}''^2} = \overline{\rho (c - \widetilde{c})^2} = \overline{\rho} (\widetilde{c}^2 - \widetilde{c}^2) = \overline{\rho} \widetilde{c} (1 - \widetilde{c}) \quad (4.5.3)$$

where progress variable can take only two values, $c = 0$ in fresh gases or $c = 1$ in burnt gases, so that $c^2 = c$. The final EBU model for the mean reaction rate, which is used for practical simulations, is:

$$\overline{\omega} = C_{EBU} \overline{\rho} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \widetilde{c} (1 - \widetilde{c}) \quad (4.5.4)$$

or in terms of fuel mass fraction:

$$\overline{\omega}_F = -C_{EBU} \overline{\rho} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \frac{\widetilde{Y}_F}{Y_F^0} \left(1 - \frac{\widetilde{Y}_F}{Y_F^0} \right) \quad (4.5.5)$$

where Y_F^0 is the initial fuel mass fraction in the reactants stream, assuming excess of oxidizer.

The simplicity of the EBU model comes from the fact that the reaction rate is written as a function of known quantities without any additional transport equations. The reaction rate in the model does not depend on the chemistry of combustion and is calculated based on the assumption of homogeneous and isentropic turbulence. The EBU model tends to overestimate the reaction rate, especially in highly strained regions, where the ratio of ε/k is large (i.e. close to walls).

4.5.2 Flame Surface Density models

The Flame Surface Density (FSD) models are based on the geometrical analysis of the flame front and provide an algebraic expression for the amount of flame surface area per unit volume Σ at each point within the premixed turbulent flame brush. Under the flamelet assumption, the mean reaction rate can be described in terms of flame surface area, as the product of the flame surface density Σ and the local consumption rate per unit of flame area [32]:

$$\overline{\omega} = \overline{\rho} s_L I_0 \Sigma \quad (4.5.6)$$

where $\bar{\rho}$ is the mean density in the reactants and I_0 is a factor for the change in the local burning velocity due to straining and curvature effects. The flame surface density measures the flame front convolutions. A high flame surface density corresponds to a high turbulent reaction rate at a given location. The advantage of this approach is a separation of the thermochemistry represented by the S_L and I_0 quantities from the turbulence/combustion interaction modeled by the flame surface density Σ . The challenge is to provide a model for the flame surface density. It is usually done by solving the following balance equation [27]:

$$\frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_i \Sigma}{\partial x_i} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\nu_t}{\sigma_\Sigma} \frac{\partial \Sigma}{\partial x_i} \right) + S_1 + S_2 + S_3 - D \quad (4.5.7)$$

where σ_Σ is the flame surface turbulent Schmidt number, ν_t is the turbulent kinematic viscosity and S_1, S_2, S_3, D are different source and sink terms that require modeling. The summary of models for closing these terms is given in [27] for different FSD models. For example in the Extended Coherent Flame Model (ECFM) [33] the following closures were incorporated:

- S_1 , which represents the flame surface production by turbulent stretch, is modeled as:

$$S_1 = \alpha \Gamma_K \frac{\varepsilon}{k} \Sigma \quad (4.5.8)$$

where Γ_K is the efficiency function in the ITNFS (Intermittent Turbulence Net Flame Stretch) model [34] and α is a model constant

- S_2 , which quantifies the production by the mean flow dilatation, is modeled as:

$$S_2 = \frac{2}{3} \frac{\partial \tilde{u}_k}{x_i} \Sigma \quad (4.5.9)$$

- S_3 , which models the effects of the flame thermal expansion and curvature:

$$S_3 = \frac{2}{3} \bar{s}_L \frac{1 - \tilde{c}}{\tilde{c}} \Sigma \quad (4.5.10)$$

- D is a destruction term due to consumption:

$$D = \beta \bar{s}_L \frac{\Sigma^2}{1 - \bar{c}} \quad (4.5.11)$$

where β is a model constant.

With some additional assumptions, such as equilibrium between source and sink terms in FSD equation, the following correlation for the mean reaction rate can be derived [26]:

$$\bar{\omega} = \bar{\rho} \frac{\alpha \varepsilon}{\beta k} (1 - \bar{c}) \quad (4.5.12)$$

recovering an EBU-type model. It shows that the EBU model can be viewed as a simplified FSD model [26].

Flame surface density models have been applied in many CFD solvers to model the turbulent premixed combustion. Also an extension to non-premixed flames has been developed by Colin and Benkenida [35] in ECFM-3Z model.

4.5.3 G-equation model

An alternative model for premixed turbulent combustion, based on the non-reacting scalar G rather than on the progress variable, has been developed by Williams [36] and improved by Peters [3]. The G -equation model is another model based on the geometrical analysis of the flame front. An equation for G can be derived by considering an iso-scalar surface:

$$G(x, t) = G_0 \quad (4.5.13)$$

As shown in Fig. 4.4, $G(x, t)$ is defined in such a way that $G > G_0$ defines the region of burnt gas and $G < G_0$ defines the region of the unburnt mixture. The choice of G_0 is arbitrary but fixed for a particular combustion event. This is called the level set approach.

The propagation of the flame front G_0 can be described by the following transport equation:

$$\frac{dx_i}{dt} = u_i + \mathbf{n} s_L \quad (4.5.14)$$

where u_i is the local flow velocity at the flame front, s_L is laminar burning velocity and \mathbf{n} is the vector normal to the front in the direction of the unburnt gas:

$$\mathbf{n} = -\frac{\nabla G}{|\nabla G|} \quad (4.5.15)$$

By differentiating the equation (4.5.13) with respect to time and introducing the equation (4.5.14) the field equation can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + u_i \cdot \nabla G = s_L \nabla |G| \quad (4.5.16)$$

which is the G -equation introduced by Williams [36]. It is applicable to thin flame structures that propagate with a well-defined burning velocity. Therefore, it is well-suited for the description of premixed turbulent combustion in the corrugated flamelets regime, where it is assumed that the laminar flame thickness is smaller than the smallest turbulent length scale, the Kolmogorov scale.

Figure 4.4: Schematic representation of the flame front as an iso-scalar surface [3].

According to Peters [3], the G -equation valid for thin reaction zones and corrugated flamelets can be derived from an order of magnitude analysis of the leading order terms for both regimes, leading to:

$$\rho \frac{\partial G}{\partial t} + \rho u_i \cdot \nabla G = (\rho s_L^0) \sigma + (\rho D) \kappa \sigma \quad (4.5.17)$$

where σ describes the absolute value of the gradient of G

$$\sigma = |\nabla G| \quad (4.5.18)$$

and κ is the curvature of the G -surface:

$$\kappa = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n} = \nabla \cdot \left(-\frac{\nabla G}{|\nabla G|} \right) \quad (4.5.19)$$

The extension of the G -equation to the entire computational domain where $G \neq G_0$ is performed by the transformation of the G -scalar field to the signed distance function:

$$|\nabla G| = 1 \quad (4.5.20)$$

Applications of the G -equation in RANS of practical combustion systems requires the use of a Favre-averaged form. Application of the Favre decomposition $G = \tilde{G} + G''$ to the standard G -equation and derivation of the transport equations of the Favre mean and variance of G are given in [3] leading to:

$$\bar{\rho} \frac{\partial \tilde{G}}{\partial t} + \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_k \cdot \nabla \tilde{G} = (\bar{\rho} s_T^0) |\nabla \tilde{G}| - \bar{\rho} D_t \tilde{\kappa} |\nabla \tilde{G}| \quad (4.5.21)$$

$$\bar{\rho} \frac{\partial \widetilde{G''^2}}{\partial t} + \bar{\rho} \tilde{u}_k \cdot \nabla \widetilde{G''^2} = \nabla_{||} \cdot (\bar{\rho} D_t \nabla_{||} \widetilde{G''^2}) + 2\bar{\rho} D_t (\nabla \tilde{G})^2 - c_s \bar{\rho} \frac{\tilde{\varepsilon}}{\tilde{k}} \widetilde{G''^2} \quad (4.5.22)$$

where s_T^0 is the turbulent flame speed, D_t is the turbulent diffusivity and c_s is the model constant. The condition $\tilde{G}(x, t) = G_0$ defines the location of the mean flame front, while the Favre variance $\widetilde{G''^2}$ represents the turbulent flame brush thickness. The required models for s_T and D_t are also derived and given in [3].

4.5.4 Probability Density Function models

Modeling turbulent premixed flames has been dominated by approaches based on the phenomenology of flamelets. Nevertheless, it is clear that the flamelet structure cannot prevail everywhere. In the flames close to extinction due to turbulent straining, or close to the flammability limits, the balance between the reaction and diffusion is weakened and

the identification of a representative flame structure becomes difficult. In such situations a Probability Density Function (PDF) might be advantageous since it makes no assumptions on the structure of the flame. It quantifies the probability $\bar{p}(Y; x, t)$ for a given location x and time t , to find a variable Y (mass fraction, progress variable, temperature, etc.) within the range $[Y - \Delta Y/2, Y + \Delta Y/2]$. The PDF fulfills the following relations, for the probability, mean and variance of the variable Y :

$$\int_Y \bar{p}(Y^*; x, t) dY^* = 1 \quad (4.5.23)$$

$$\int_Y Y^* \bar{p}(Y^*; x, t) dY^* = \bar{Y}(x, t) \quad (4.5.24)$$

$$\int_Y (Y^* - \bar{Y})^2 \bar{p}(Y^*; x, t) dY^* = \overline{Y'^2}(x, t) \quad (4.5.25)$$

where Y^* is the sample space variable corresponding to the random variable Y . The mean burning rate or any mean quantity may be estimated as:

$$\bar{\omega}_Y(x, t) = \int_Y \dot{\omega}_Y(Y^*) \bar{p}(Y^*) dY^* \quad (4.5.26)$$

Probability density functions can be defined in any turbulent reacting flow field and contain all the required information to describe unsteady effects. Quantities such as $\dot{\omega}_Y(Y^*)$ are provided from chemistry and laminar flame studies. The difficulty is to determine the PDF, which changes at every point in the flow field. Two main directions may be chosen to build numerical models from PDF — to presume the PDF shape or to solve a balance equation for the PDF.

Chapter 5

Spark Ignition models for combustion modeling in SI engines

The description of the ignition process by a spark discharge given in Chapter 3 gives an overview on the complexity of this phenomenon. The spark discharge can be divided into three phases — plasma breakdown, arc discharge and glow discharge which all have particular electrical properties and different heat losses and energy transfer efficiencies [1]. As a result only a part of the deposited energy is available for the initiation of the ignition, while the most of the energy is lost due to heat conduction, plasma expansion and radiation. The inflammation of the mixture by the spark plasma is a complicated phenomenon itself. The high temperatures in the center of the spark channel are much too high for stable combustion products to exist. The steep gradients of radicals and temperatures that occur at the plasma surface imply considerable gradients in concentrations of radicals which contribute to the flame initiation. The heat and radicals transferred from the spark towards unburned mixture combined with fairly suitable temperatures for the formation of stable molecules lead to an acceleration of the combustion reactions at the outer plasma surface where the conditions are ideal for the rapid chemical activity [1, 4]. All of these processes are strongly dependent on the electrodes temperature, geometry (width, shape and gap size), local flowfield, turbulence or spark energy and power [37] affecting the flame kernel formation. Finally, after the breakdown, chemical reactions have to produce enough energy to overcome heat losses and the kernel has to grow beyond a critical size or quenching will occur [37].

The spark ignition process has been studied extensively in the past. A number of publications on experimental and numerical investigation of the spark ignition can be found [1, 10, 19, 20, 22, 37–45]. Although the ignition process is understood, its complexity makes numerical description difficult. It is desirable to include all occurring phenomena in the ignition model to reflect the real process as close as possible. Hence, existing numerical models [19, 37–43, 45, 46] usually focus on the spark discharge and early kernel formation. Although these models are quite detailed, their application into the CFD codes would require resolution of very short time scales (less than 10^{-6} s) and very small length scales (ranging from the spark gap distance to the integral length scale) leading to very fine meshes and time steps, which may not be practical in commercial engineering applications. These limitations lead to the development of simplified phenomenological models of the spark ignition and early flame kernel formation which are coupled with regular combustion models. In order to account for the details of the ignition process, the ignition models implemented into the CFD codes are usually based on the tracking of the particles that can represent the spark arc, flame kernels or early flame surface propagation independently of the grid size. This chapter reviews the spark ignition models that have been developed and successfully applied to 3D CFD combustion simulations. The simplifications of reviewed models are underlined, which is a basis for the development of a new ignition model proposed in this work.

5.1 Lagrangian models for flame kernel development

5.1.1 Discrete Particle Ignition Kernel (DPIK) by Fan et al.

One of the first proposed models based on the tracking of Lagrangian particles was the Discrete Particle Ignition Kernel (DPIK) model proposed by Fan et al. [47]. In the paper authors described models for spray, spark plug, ignition, combustion and emissions that they incorporated in the KIVA software. In the DPIK ignition model the flame kernel is assumed to be spherical and is described using particle markers (Fig. 5.1). This method has the advantage of reducing the sensitivity of the results to grid size effects which are unavoidable during the early stage of the ignition process when the flame kernel is smaller than the grid size. However, the kernel size is not restricted to be smaller than the grid

size. Authors claim that with a mesh size of about 3 mm typical kernel size could be as large as 3 mm.

Figure 5.1: Discrete Particle Ignition Kernel (DPIK) model [47].

In the model the initial kernel size is set to 0.5 mm [44] and particles move in the radial direction with velocities that depend on the turbulence, equivalence ratio, temperature and pressure in the spark region. The particle velocity components are calculated as:

$$u_p = \left[\frac{T_{ad}}{T} s_L + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k} \right] \quad (5.1.1)$$

where the parameter $\frac{T_{ad}}{T}$ accounts for thermal expansion effects, where T_{ad} is the adiabatic flame temperature and T is an estimated local gas temperature based on adiabatic expansion:

$$T = T_{k1} \left(\frac{P_{k1}}{P_{k2}} \right)^{1-\frac{1}{\gamma}} \quad (5.1.2)$$

where T_{k1} and P_{k1} are the temperature and pressure at the start of the ignition, P_{k2} is pressure inside the kernel region after the start of combustion, γ is a constant between 1.3 and 1.4, k is the turbulent kinetic energy and s_L is laminar flame speed from Metghalchi and Keck [48] which accounts for equivalence ratio ϕ , residual gas fraction R and local gas temperature T obtained from 5.1.2.

The flame kernel diameter in each step is calculated as follows:

$$D_{kernel} = 2 \cdot \left[\frac{T_{ad}}{T} s_L + \sqrt{\frac{2}{3}k} \right] \cdot (t - t_0) + D_0 \quad (5.1.3)$$

where $(t - t_0)$ is the elapsed time from the start of ignition and D_0 is the initial kernel size.

The kernel flame surface density in each cell is calculated as:

$$\Sigma = \frac{N_{cell}}{N_{total}} \frac{\pi D_{kernel}^2}{V_{cell}} \frac{\theta_f}{2\pi} \quad (5.1.4)$$

where N_{total} is the total number of particles (3000 for three-dimensional cases), N_{cell} is the total number of particles in a specified cell, V_{cell} is the cell volume and θ_f is the sectional angle of the mesh if the mesh represents only a section of the whole combustion chamber.

For simplicity, a one step reaction is adopted in the kernel flame growth process:

The burn rate is calculated as:

$$\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = -C_w \cdot \min\left(\frac{\rho_f}{\text{MW}_f C_{st,f}}, \frac{\rho_{\text{O}_2}}{\text{MW}_{\text{O}_2} C_{st,\text{O}_2}}\right) \cdot \Sigma_{SL} \text{MW}_i C_{st,i} \quad (5.1.6)$$

where MW_i is the molecular weight of species i , $C_{st,i}$ are stoichiometric coefficients, C_w is used to account for the wrinkling effect of the kernel surface.

After the kernel size reaches the order of the integral length scale the model switches to the time scale combustion model also described by the authors [47]:

$$D_{kernel} \geq C_k l_I \quad (5.1.7)$$

where C_k equals 3.5 and l_I is the turbulence length scale related to the turbulence kinetic energy k and its dissipation rate ε as:

$$l_I = 0.16 \frac{k^{1.5}}{\varepsilon} \quad (5.1.8)$$

with a turbulence field modeled using the RNG $k - \varepsilon$ model of Han and Reitz [49].

The DPIK kernel model was tuned and validated against experimental data for homogeneous SI engine from Hampson et al. [50]. The results agreed well with the experiments and the model was less sensitive to the numerical grid resolution effects than other existing ignition models. However, the DPIK model still does not account for such ignition phe-

nomena as the plasma breakdown, arc discharge or glow phase, especially. Furthermore, the spark plug heat transfer is not considered in the model, what can strongly affect the flame kernel development and the whole combustion process.

5.1.2 Improvement of the DPIK model by Tan and Reitz

To improve the prediction accuracy of the spark ignition and combustion processes in spark ignition engines Tan and Reitz [51] proposed improved ignition and flame propagation models and implemented them in the KIVA-3V CFD code. The flamelet combustion model is based on the G -equation [3] combustion model which tracks a discontinuous surface and describes the interface evolution. Transport equations for mean \bar{G} and its variance $\overline{G'^2}$, which are related to the mean flame position and the flame brush thickness, respectively, are formulated, and the instantaneous flame location within the flame brush is described by a PDF (presumed probability density function). The ignition model is based on the previously described DPIK model [47]. This method allows to track the growth of the kernel which is smaller than the computational cell size.

The calculation starts after the breakdown period and the ignition kernel is assumed to be spherical with radius of 0.5 mm. The ignition kernel flame is very thin and separates the burned and unburned gas. The temperature and all reactive scalars jump from their values in unburned mixture to the corresponding equilibrium values in the burned gas. The pressure is assumed to be uniform inside and outside the kernel and the temperature to be uniform inside the kernel. The kernel surface is located in front of the flame, and thus, no heat transfer between the kernel and unburned gas is calculated.

The model description starts with the ignition kernel mass-burning rate \dot{m}_k , which is also the increase in the flame kernel mass:

$$\dot{m}_k = \frac{dm_k}{dt} = \rho_u A_k s_{eff} = \rho_u A_k (s_T + s_{plasma}) \quad (5.1.9)$$

where ρ_u is the unburned gas density, A_k is the flame kernel surface area and s_{eff} is the effective kernel growth speed that consists of turbulent flame speed s_T and the so-called plasma velocity s_{plasma} which results from the spark discharge energy.

The equation describing the kernel expansion rate (and the movement of the kernel particles) derived by the authors of the model is as follows:

$$\frac{dr_k}{dt} = \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_k} (s_T + s_{plasma}) \quad (5.1.10)$$

where ρ_u is the unburned gas density, ρ_k is the gas density within the flame kernel and s_{plasma} is the plasma velocity obtained from the energy balance for the control volume surrounded by ignition kernel surface:

$$s_{plasma} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{spk} \cdot \eta_{eff}}{4\pi r_k^2 \left[\rho_u (U_k - h_u) + p \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_k} \right]} \quad (5.1.11)$$

where \dot{Q}_{spk} is the electrical energy transfer rate to the kernel, η_{eff} is the efficiency of the energy transfer [44] and U_k is the specific internal energy of the burned gas within the flame kernel.

During the ignition, kernel formation and initial kernel growth processes, the turbulence integral length scale is typically much larger than the kernel size, so that the kernel can only sense the high-frequency fraction of the turbulent spectrum. The influence of the kernel size on the turbulent flame velocity s_T is included through correlation for s_T proposed by Herweg and Maly in [44].

The species density changes are calculated by:

$$\frac{d\rho_i}{dt} = C_w \rho (Y_i^u - Y_i^b) \Sigma s_T \quad (5.1.12)$$

where flame surface density Σ is calculated as in equation (5.1.3), C_w is a constant chosen to be equal to 10 to assure complete combustion inside the ignition kernel. Y_i^u and Y_i^b are the mass fractions of species i , in the unburned and burned gas, respectively and ρ is the gas density.

Once the ignition kernel exceeds a critical radius that is related to the integral turbulent length scale l of the flow field:

$$r_{k2} \geq C_{m1} l = C_{m1} \cdot 0.16 \frac{1.5k}{\varepsilon} \quad (5.1.13)$$

the ignition model switches to the G -equation combustion model with G -scalar field initialized according to the final flame kernel surface provided by the ignition model.

Authors validated their models against experimental data by Maly and Vogel [15]. In general, the agreement with the experimental data was considered to be satisfactory. However, model underestimates the measured kernel radius, partially due to uncertainties associated with the specification of the initial spark breakdown event.

5.1.3 DPIK based model by Falfari and Bianchi

Another model based on the DPIK was proposed by Falfari and Bianchi in [52]. In their model, firstly, a lump model for the electrical circuit of the spark plug is used to compute the breakdown and glow energy. At the end of the shock wave and very first plasma expansion, a spherical kernel is deposited inside the gas flow at the spark plug location. A simple model allows one to compute the initial flame kernel radius and temperature based on physical mixture properties and spark plug characteristics. The spherical surface of the kernel is discretized by triangular elements which move radially according to a Lagrangian approach. The expansion velocity is computed accounting for both heat conduction effect at the highest temperatures and thermodynamic energy balance at relatively lower temperatures. Turbulence effects and thermodynamic properties of the air-fuel mixture are accounted for. One of the main differences and improvements in regard to the two previously described models is a possibility of the spark restrikes depending on the gas flow velocity and mixture quality at the spark location. The proposed 1D/Lagrangian ignition model is closely coupled with the KIVA3 CFD solver.

The first part of the ignition model is the electrical sub-model which provides the initial conditions for the flame kernel expansion model. For simplicity the phase of the electric arc and the plasma formation is not modeled. The electrical model computes the breakdown energy and the electrical power released to the gas flow during the glow phase. At the end of the plasma shock wave dynamics after the breakdown event, a spherical flame kernel of initial radius r_i and initial temperature T_i is evaluated according to [18,53] and deposited into the gas flow in the cell where spark plug is located:

$$T_i = \left[\frac{1}{k} \left(\frac{T_b}{T_u} \right) + 1 \right] T_u \quad (5.1.14)$$

$$r_i = \left[\frac{k}{k-1} \cdot \frac{E_{bd}}{p \cdot d_{gap} \left(1 - \frac{T_u}{T_i}\right) \pi} \right]^{1/2} \quad (5.1.15)$$

where the breakdown temperature T_b is assumed to be 60000 K.

The sphere representing the kernel is discretized by a set of triangular elements which move radially depending on burning rate and thermal expansion. The flame kernel expansion sub-model is based on the Herweg and Maly model [44] where the kernel radius change in time is based on the ratio of unburned to burned density:

$$\frac{dr_k}{dt} = \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_k} s_l \cdot - \left[\frac{V_k}{A_k} \left(\frac{1}{T_k} \frac{dT_k}{dt} - \frac{1}{p} \frac{dp}{dt} \right) \right] \quad (5.1.16)$$

where pressure p in equation is assumed to be uniform in burned and fresh gases, while the kernel temperature T_k evaluation is divided into two phases with a transition at $T_k = 3T_{ad}$ as proposed in [54].

During the first phase when $T_k \geq 3T_{ad}$ the flame kernel expansion is dominated by heat conduction from burned to fresh mixture which prevails over the contribution given by reaction rate. The temperature variation of the kernel is evaluated by solving the heat conduction equation for the space-dependent plasma temperature T_{pl} according to [44]:

$$\frac{\partial T_{pl}}{\partial t} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_{pl}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial T_{pl}}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{P - \dot{Q}_w}{\rho c_p V_k} \quad (5.1.17)$$

which assumes that the heat is dissipated in all directions and the thermal diffusivity is constant. The power P comes from the power released by the electrical circuit and \dot{Q}_w represents the heat power lost to the electrodes. The solution of (5.1.17) provides the kernel temperature space and time-dependent evolution and is decoupled from the main CFD solver in order to account for sub-cycle time step. The kernel temperature T_k is taken as the average distribution in space of the plasma temperature T_{pl} between $r = 0$ and $r = r_k$ at a certain instant.

When the kernel temperature T_k drops below $3T_{ad}$ the heat conduction from burned to fresh gases becomes negligible. During the second phase of the process the kernel temperature is estimated by applying an energy balance equation for the open system, assuming that the system is in thermodynamic equilibrium, the general gas law holds and

the pressure is uniform in burned and fresh gases:

$$\frac{dh_k}{dt} = \frac{1}{m_k} \left[\frac{dQ_{ch}}{dt} + \frac{dE_{ele}}{dt} - \frac{dQ_w}{dt} + V_k \frac{dp}{dt} \right] - \frac{h_k}{m_k} \frac{dm_k}{dt} \quad (5.1.18)$$

where E_{ele} is the energy supplied by the spark plug, Q_{ch} is the energy contribution from chemical reactions, Q_w the energy lost at walls. The kernel temperature T_k , and the kernel density ρ_k are derived from the specific enthalpy.

In order to couple the mass and the energy with the CFD solver, firstly the flame surface density Σ is reconstructed in each cell:

$$\Sigma_i = \frac{\Xi}{V_i} \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{k=1}^M A_{k,j} \quad (5.1.19)$$

with Ξ being the flame wrinkling factor, M being the number of triangular elements lying in i -th cell having an area $A_{k,j}$, N being the total number of computational cells where the flame front is located and V_i being the volume of i -th cell. Then the mass and energy coupling with the main CFD solver occurs by computing the fuel consumption rate in the i -th cell accordingly to the ECFM model [33]

$$\dot{\omega}_{k,i} = \rho_u s_{L,k} \Sigma_i \quad (5.1.20)$$

When the kernel radius reaches 2.0 mm, the switch to the flamelet ECFM main combustion model occurs. The ECFM takes as initial conditions for the flame surface density Σ the latest value available in each computational cell occupied by the flame front.

Falfari and Bianchi validated their model with experimental data by Herweg and Maly [44]. The model has shown to be capable of reproducing the physics of the ignition process. A slight underprediction of the flame speed was present in almost all conditions.

5.2 Arc and Kernel Tracking Ignition Model (AK-TIM)

Previously described DPIK models [47, 51, 52] do not account for the details of the spark deposition and its interaction with the flow which may affect the early flame kernel development. Although in [52] some parameters of the secondary electrical circuit are

included, the electrical arc development is not considered. Hence, it is questionable if the restrikes are modeled correctly.

For describing the early combustion phase in a more complete manner, Duclos and Colin [11] developed a numerical model called AKTIM (Arc and Kernel Tracking Ignition Model). This model is based on four main submodels combined. The first submodel describes the geometry of the spark plug and its interaction with the chamber flow, the second one models the spark channel by a set of Lagrangian particles placed along the spark path, the third describes the secondary electrical circuit of the spark plug and the fourth describes the flame kernels represented by Lagrangian marker particles. Nowadays, spark plug geometry is usually included in the 3D CFD simulations. The original model for the spark plug will not be described.

Electrical Circuit Model

The authors of AKTIM provide the model of the electrical circuit based on a simplified scheme of a classical inductive system. When the switch opens at the time of ignition, a part of the energy stored in the primary inductance is transferred to secondary circuit and the spark plug. The initial energy in the secondary circuit $E_s(0)$, the resistance R_s and the inductance L_s are given as input parameters. After a few μs the voltage reaches the breakdown voltage V_{bd} and a spark is formed between the electrodes. During the next few μs an amount of electrical energy E_{bd} is transmitted to the gas as in equation:

$$E_{bd} = \frac{V_{bd}^2}{C_{bd}^2 d_{ie}} \quad (5.2.1)$$

The main spark phase (glow phase) lasts a few ms, corresponding to the visible spark observed in experiments. During this phase, the voltage between the electrodes V_{ie} is given by the relation:

$$V_{ie}(t) = V_{cf} + V_{af} + V_{gc} \quad (5.2.2)$$

where V_{cf} and V_{af} are the cathode and anode voltage falls (constants) and V_{gc} is the voltage along the spark path given by the relation:

$$V_{gc} = 40.46 \cdot l_{spark} i_s^{-0.32} p^{0.51} \quad (5.2.3)$$

where l_{spk} is the spark length, p is the pressure and i_s is the current in the secondary circuit given by:

$$i_s = \sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{L_s}} \quad (5.2.4)$$

while the electrical energy available on the secondary circuit is:

$$\frac{dE_s(t)}{dt} = -R_s i_s^2(t) - V_{ie} i_s(t) \quad (5.2.5)$$

During the glow phase the inter-electrode voltage V_{ie} may reach the breakdown voltage and new breakdown occurs: the previous spark vanishes and a new one is created. The glow phase lasts as long as the electrical energy is available in the circuit.

Spark Model

At the instant of the breakdown a spark is initiated between the electrodes. In AKTIM it is represented by a set of Lagrangian particles originally equally spaced between the electrodes. These particles are transported by the mean flow except the ones at the spark extremities. The distance between adjacent spark particles is maintained inside a given range so that particles are added or removed permanently. In the case of strong convection at the spark plug, the spark length can be many times larger than the inter-electrode distance d_{ie} , involving a direct increase of the gas column voltage V_{gc} that can lead to a new breakdown. In case of a breakdown, the spark particles are suppressed and a new set of particles corresponding to a new spark is initiated. The model is thus capable of handling multiple breakdowns.

Flame Kernel Model

The flame kernel is described using marker particles. However, unlike in the DPIK model by Fan et al. [47], the set of particles does not represent a sole kernel. Each of the total N_k particles represents the gravity center of a possible flame kernel, having a statistical weight $1/N_K$. Each flame kernel is initially a sphere of imposed 0.005 mm radius. The evolution of each flame kernel is determined by its excess of energy E^i and

its burned gas mass m_K^i :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dm_K^i}{dt} = \rho_{fr} A_{eff}^i s_{L,eff}^i \\ \frac{dE_K^i}{dt} = Q_e - Q_w^i \end{cases} \quad (5.2.6)$$

where Q_e is the energy received from the electric circuit, Q_w^i is the energy lost to the walls, ρ_{fr} is the fresh gas density, A_{eff}^i is the effective kernel surface and $s_{L,eff}^i$ is the effective laminar flame speed. The effective flame surface is calculated as:

$$A_{eff}^i = 4\pi \left(\frac{3m_b^i}{4\pi\rho_K^i} \right)^{2/3} \cdot F_{str} \quad (5.2.7)$$

where F_{str} is a convection factor and kernel density ρ_K^i depends on the local burned gas density and kernel excess of energy through:

$$\rho_K^i = \rho_b^i \left(1 + \frac{E_K^i}{c_{p,b} T_b} \right)^{-1} \quad (5.2.8)$$

The equation 5.2.7 uses the assumption that the flame kernel is spherical at the initialization. Afterwards, the surface is distorted both by the mean flow and turbulent fluctuations, which is accounted for with the F_{str} coefficient. The effective laminar flame speed is calculated with the correlation proposed by Pischinger and Heywood [46]:

$$s_{L,eff}^i = s_L^0 \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\sqrt{1 + \frac{T_K^i - T_b}{100} \frac{\delta_L}{\delta_L + r_K^i}} - 1 \right) \right] \quad (5.2.9)$$

where r_K^i is the radius of the kernel and δ_L is the local laminar flame thickness. During the glow phase, the surface of the burning kernel is deposited randomly as flame surface density in a cell contained into the kernel volume, thus initializing the ECFM model. When the combustion of the flame kernel ends, further flame propagation is handled by the ECFM model.

The original AKTIM model [11] was validated with experimental data from an optical engine [55] operating in PFI mode with a propane/air equivalence ratio of 0.9 at 1200 rpm. The spark timing was set to 25° CA BTDC. Simulations were performed with KIVA-MB solver and ECFM combustion model. Results show a good agreement between the model and the experiment. The model correctly simulates the increase in electrical

energy transferred to the flame kernel and the decrease in the flame kernel heat loss when the convection at the spark plug is increased. It also shows that transition between the AKTIM model and the 3D combustion ECFM model is weakly dependent on the instant of transition proving that the flame kernel development is consistent with the 3D combustion model.

5.3 Spark Channel Monitoring Models

5.3.1 Spark Channel Ignition Monitoring Model (SparkCIMM)

Another approach for spark ignition modeling in DISI engines was proposed by Dahms et al. [9, 24, 56]. Based on high-speed imaging data showing complexity of the spark discharge process (formation, turbulent stretching and wrinkling, multiple restrikes) and ignition process (localized flame kernel formation and growth) they proposed to monitor the local mixture ignitability along the spark channel over the duration of a typical spark (2 ms), even after a flame kernel has been initiated. Whenever local conditions along the spark channel permit ignition, a flame kernel is launched and tracked as it grows and merges with other kernels to form the turbulent flame surface. The local mixture-fraction variance is incorporated into both the early-kernel-growth model and the G -equation flamelet model that takes over once the flame surface can be resolved on the computational grid. This approach yields early flame-location probabilities in much better agreement with experiment than simpler ignition models that do not monitor the mixture composition along the extended, moving spark channel or that ignore the effect of the mixture fraction variance on the propagating flame.

Spark-channel evolution

The spark channel is too thin to resolve by conventional computational grids. Hence, similarly as in AKTIM model, the spark channel is modeled by computational particles (size 50 μm) that define its shape and track its local mixture composition, motion and turbulent wrinkling. As the local flow field elongates the spark channel, new particles are introduced to maintain a uniform distribution along the channel. For each particle, the local mixture fraction Z_p is computed as the sum of the interpolated local mean mixture fraction \widetilde{Z}_p and a random sub-grid turbulent fluctuation $\widetilde{Z''^2_{sub,p}}$. Particle advection by the

local flow field is modeled similarly as the sum of the interpolated local mean flow and a random sub-grid turbulent velocity. Other particle quantities are interpolated from the grid cell centers to the particle positions as illustrated in Fig. 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Procedure for evaluating the spark channel mixture stratification in SparkCIMM model based on computational cell quantities [9].

The mixture ignitability (considering the local charge stratification, dilution, and temperature, which is particularly important near the spark plug) is computed at each particle location. For every particle encountering the ignitable mixture, a small flame kernel is launched. The ignitability criterion is based on the local Karlovitz number: $Ka = (v_\eta/s_{L,eff})^2 < Ka_{ad}$ [3], where v_η is the Kolmogorov-scale eddy turnover velocity and $s_{L,eff} = s_L + s_{plasma}$ is an effective laminar burning velocity that includes the intrinsic laminar burning velocity s_l and a *plasma* expansion velocity due to spark energy deposition. The ignition fails for high values of Ka , for which Kolmogorov eddies can disrupt the inner reaction layer of the flame (the *broken reaction zones* region in the regime diagram for premixed turbulent combustion [3]).

The effect of restrikes on the ignition is included in the model by resetting the spark marker particles to their original locations when the spark channel exceeds a predefined length (10 mm) determined from experiments. Several restrikes may occur during the assumed 2 ms spark duration with additional small flame kernels initiated as local conditions permit.

Early flame-kernel development

When local conditions permit ignition at a particle position, a small (0.5 mm) flame kernel is initiated and its growth on the sub-grid scale is modeled including mixture-fraction fluctuations. Multiple flame kernels grow spherically due to the turbulent flame

speed, advect at the local flow velocity, and merge until they form a turbulent flame surface that can be resolved on the computational grid. Merging different flame kernels is modeled by enveloping flame surface of intersecting kernels. The radius of each flame kernel is evaluated from:

$$r_k = \sqrt[3]{\frac{3m_k}{4\pi\rho_b}} \quad (5.3.1)$$

with ρ_b as the density of the burned gas and the flame-kernel mass m_k obtained from continuity equation

$$\frac{dm_k}{dt} = 4\pi r_k^2 \rho_u s_{T,\kappa} \quad (5.3.2)$$

with $s_{T,\kappa}$ being the turbulent burning velocity including the mixture-fraction variance which is derived in the original paper [9].

The density in the burned gas can be significantly lower than the density of adiabatic burned gas at temperature T_{ad} due to the increased kernel temperature T_K caused by electrical energy deposition at rate \dot{Q}_{spk} . This effect is modeled as follows:

$$\frac{dT_K}{dt} = -\frac{\dot{m}_K}{m_K}(T_K - T_{ad}) + \frac{\dot{Q}_{spk}\eta_{eff}}{m_K c_p} + \frac{1}{\rho_b c_p} \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (5.3.3)$$

where η_{eff} is the efficiency of the electrical energy transfer to the gas, c_p is the specific heat and p is the pressure. As soon as the flame can be resolved on the computational grid, the G -equation approach is used to transport the mean turbulent flame surface [3].

The SparkCIMM model includes several physical processes that have been shown experimentally to be important for the ignition under the highly stratified and diluted charge conditions that characterize part-load spray-guided gasoline engine operation. Previously described DPIK [47, 51, 52] and AKTIM [11] models do not include these physical processes. In the DPIK model, the spark channel structure is neglected entirely and a single flame kernel grows spherically by spark-energy input and flame propagation without advection until it is large enough to be followed by the G -equation simulation. Both the DPIK and AKTIM approaches ignore the effects of turbulent equivalence-ratio fluctuations on early flame-kernel development. The SparkCIMM model is also based on some simplifications. The energy deposited by the spark into the mixture is treated as constant

in time, whereas the DPIK and AKTIM approaches use time-dependent energy deposition based on experiments. The restrike criterion here is also simpler than that in AKTIM and is based only on the prescribed threshold for the length of the spark.

5.3.2 Curved Arc Diffusion Ignition Model (CADIM)

Another ignition model based on the tracking of the spark channel was proposed by Schäfer et al. in [8, 57]. The model accounts for the spark-channel deflection and curvature, diffusion processes, chemical kinetics and the location and propagation of the first flame kernels. Four submodels which simulate the spark-channel dynamics, ignition delay time, flame kernel formation and transition to the combustion model are introduced. The model was implemented into ANSYS-CFX CFD solver and combined with the G -equation combustion model for modeling the spark ignition process in SI engines.

Particle evolution model

When the ignition crank angle is reached, a thin spark channel ($d_{spk} = 0.05$ mm) is generated between spark electrodes as evenly distributed Lagrangian marker particles. The particles are massless and one-way coupled to the flow field, which means that particles move according to the velocity interpolated from 3D flow. All thermodynamic and chemical conditions are directly evaluated at the spark-channel marker particles.

Figure 5.3: Illustration of the spark channel curvature in CADIM model [57].

Ignition delay time

Under the assumption that the ignition process and the ignition delay time depend only on the local temperature, pressure and mixture fraction, a simultaneous ignition along

the entire spark-channel should occur. However, experimental investigations presented by the authors of the model suggests that the flame develops at a distinct position along the deflected spark channel. Hence, they decided to derive and solve 1D mass and heat diffusion equations with curvature terms in the normal direction to the spark channel surface. An illustration of the spark channel curvature calculation for a single particle is given in Fig. 5.3. The governing equations for the species and the temperature are:

$$\rho \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\rho D_k \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial K} \right) - \kappa_K \rho D_k \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial K} + \sum_{m=1}^n \left[Y_k \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\rho D_m \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial K} \right) - \kappa_K Y_k \rho D_m \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial K} + \rho D_m \frac{\partial Y_k}{\partial K} \frac{\partial Y_m}{\partial K} \right] + \dot{m}_k \quad (5.3.4)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \right) - \kappa_K \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} - \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \sum_{k=1}^n (c_p - c_{pk}) \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{h_k}{c_p} \dot{m}_k + \dot{Q}_e + \dot{Q}_w \quad (5.3.5)$$

where K is the 1D domain in the normal direction to the spark channel surface, Y_k is the mass fraction of the species k , and κ_K is the spark surface curvature at the location of given particle. \dot{Q}_e and \dot{Q}_w are heat input from the spark channel and wall losses, both implemented as boundary conditions for 1D model. The solution of the equation system is the temperature profile and species concentrations along the K -domain. A decreased overall curvature of the surface (corresponding to more deflected channel) results in decreased heat and mass diffusion, which eventually leads to increased temperature and shorter ignition delay. As soon as the mixture ignites due to heat input from the spark channel, an initial flame kernel is introduced at the location of the given particle.

Kernel growth and transition to combustion model

The introduced flame kernel is usually too small to be resolved on the regular engine computational mesh and its expansion is initially calculated based on the ratio of unburned and burned density multiplied by the kernel expansion speed s_K :

$$\frac{dr_k}{dt} = \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_b} s_K \quad (5.3.6)$$

where s_K is calculated as:

$$s_K = \max \left(s_L, s_T - \frac{2}{r_k} D_t \right) \quad (5.3.7)$$

where, s_L is the laminar flame speed, s_T is the turbulent flame speed, factor $2/r_k$ accounts for the curvature of the flame kernel and the turbulent diffusivity D_t considers influence of the turbulence on the small flame kernel. During the kernel growth, the G -scalar in the G -equation model is computed by enforcing a spherical distribution with G_0 located at a distance r_K from the ignition point. At the moment when flame kernel reaches the threshold value defined by the user, flame propagation is handled by the G -equation combustion model.

Authors of the model performed a validation based on the measurements from a BMW turbo-charged 3-cylinder DISI engine. Available measurements were pressure traces and flame contours during the combustion process visualized with a special equipment. Comparison of measurements and calculations showed a good agreement under different engine loads.

5.3.3 Lagrangian flame-kernel model by Cornolti et al.

The next recently developed model that is based on the spark channel tracking was presented by Cornolti et al. [58]. Authors pointed out that the already available models are focused on particular aspects of the ignition process but none of them accounts for all the phenomena. For example, the DPIK-derived models are very detailed in the computation of flame surface density and initial thermal expansion of the ignited volume, but effects of local flow and air-fuel ratio distribution are almost neglected. On the other hand, AKTIM and Spark-CIMM describe very carefully how the initial flame development is affected by the flow and turbulence, but effects of the energy transfer on the flame kernel growth are taken into account in a simplified way. The model proposed by Cornolti et al. is a first approach to combine the most advanced aspects of the available ignition models. In particular, the spark channel is represented by a set of Lagrangian particles, which are initially placed along the spark gap [9]. Particles are convected by the mean flow and, for all of them, equations of mass and energy are solved. Specific submodels estimate the instantaneous amount of the energy transferred from the electrical circuit

to the kernels and calculate the flame expansion velocity accordingly, taking into account the real properties of the high-temperature gas [59]. At each time step, the flame surface density distribution is reconstructed once particles positions and their radii are known [52]. Such quantity is then used in the combustion model to calculate the fuel burning rate.

Particle evolution model

The breakdown is a strong non-equilibrium thermodynamic process which lasts for a few nanoseconds, therefore it is not modeled. The initial temperature and diameter of the particles are set with the presumed value assumed after the breakdown using the equations suggested in the work by Song and Sunwoo [53] (similarly as in the DPIK model [51]). The temperatures obtained by these equations are of the order of 40000 K and make the initial thermal expansion not negligible. Once particles are introduced in the computational mesh, they are convected by the mean flow, with their position x_p changing according to the gas velocity at the particle position. Each spark particle represents a possible location of an ignition kernel. For each of the kernels, the mass and energy conservation equations are solved. Both mass conservation and radius variation equations account for contributions due to thermal expansion and turbulent flame speed and are described by the modified equations from [52]:

$$\frac{dm_p}{dt} = 4\pi r_p^2 \rho_u (s_T + \frac{\rho_k}{\rho_u} s_{plasma}) \quad (5.3.8)$$

$$\frac{dr_p}{dt} = \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_k} (s_T + s_{plasma}) \quad (5.3.9)$$

with r_p being the particle radius and ρ_u the unburned gas density at particle position. s_T is the turbulent flame speed, which is computed from the laminar flame speed s_L at the particle position and the flame wrinkling Ξ :

$$s_T = \Xi \cdot s_L \quad (5.3.10)$$

To compute the second RHS term in Equation (5.3.8), representing the flame kernel expansion velocity due to energy transfer from the electrical circuit, it is necessary to distinguish between the two different mechanisms governing flame kernel growth:

- heat conduction from the hot plasma channel to the unburned mixture, during which the temperature distribution inside the flame kernel is not uniform,
- expansion due to chemical reactions and heat transfer from the electrical circuit, during which the temperature is uniform inside the flame kernel and the composition is at chemical equilibrium.

Plasma channel model

When $T_p > 3T_{ad}$ heat conduction effects cannot be neglected in the gas surrounding the ignited kernel. For this reason, the temperature distribution and its effects on s_{plasma} need to be modeled in detail. All the flame kernels related to the same discharge event are assumed to have the same temperature distribution, which is computed by solving the heat conduction equation for the space-dependent plasma temperature T_{pl} , similarly as in [52] :

$$\frac{\partial T_{pl}}{\partial t} = \alpha \left(\frac{\partial^2 T_{pl}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial T_{pl}}{\partial r} \right) + \frac{\eta_{eff} \cdot \dot{Q}_{spk}}{\rho_{pl} c_{p,pl} \cdot V_{pl}} \quad (5.3.11)$$

where α is the plasma thermal diffusivity. A sub-cycling procedure is used to solve Equation (5.3.11), which is discretized on a 1D, axy-symmetric grid representing a sector of the gas region that surrounds the spark electrodes. The mesh height is set to be equal to d_{gap} , while the radial length of the domain is set to 1 cm, which is significantly higher than the maximum diameter of the flame kernel that is reached during this phase. The grid size is 10 μm and the following initial and boundary conditions are imposed at spark time and after each restrike event:

$$\begin{cases} t = t_0 : T_{pl} = T_i & \text{if } 0 < r < r_i, & T_{pl} = T_u & \text{if } r < r_i \\ r = r_\infty : T_{pl} = T_u \end{cases} \quad (5.3.12)$$

where T_i and r_i are the temperature and the radius after the breakdown, respectively. Following Herweg and Maly [44], at each time step the flame kernel radius r_k is identified as the location where the adiabatic flame temperature is found in the spark-channel 1D mesh. In this way, the expansion velocity s_{plasma} can be computed as follows:

$$s_{plasma} = \frac{r_k(t + \delta t_{CFD}) - r_k(t)}{\delta t_{CFD}} \quad (5.3.13)$$

To properly solve Equation (5.3.11), temperature dependency of the plasma properties such as thermal diffusivity α_{pl} , heat capacity $c_{p,pl}$ and density ρ_{pl} need to be known. These effects were taken into account by assuming thermodynamic and chemical equilibrium and neglecting fuel contribution. In this way, it was possible to employ the thermodynamic and transport properties functions provided in [59].

At the lower temperatures, when the flame kernel expansion is mainly governed by chemical reactions, the temperature T_p inside the flame kernel can be considered as uniform and is computed through the following energy conservation equation:

$$\frac{dT_p}{dt} = -\frac{m_p}{\dot{m}_p}(T_p - T_b) + \frac{\dot{Q}_{spk}\eta_{eff}}{m_p c_p} + \frac{1}{\rho_b c_p} \frac{dp}{dt} \quad (5.3.14)$$

with ρ_b being the burned gas density and T_b the adiabatic flame temperature. While s_{plasma} is computed according to [9, 51]:

$$s_{plasma} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{spk} \cdot \eta_{eff}}{4\pi r_k^2 \left[(u_k - h_u) + p \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_k} \right]} \quad (5.3.15)$$

where \dot{Q}_{spk} is the energy transferred from the electrical circuit, η_{eff} is the efficiency of the energy transfer, h_u is the specific enthalpy of the flame kernel, u_k and ρ_k are the kernel specific enthalpy and density, respectively.

Electrical circuit submodel

The electrical circuit submodel is similar to the AKTIM model [11]. After the spark-time, the primary switch is opened and the voltage across the electrode rapidly reaches the breakdown value. After that the same equations as in AKTIM are solved for the secondary circuit of the electrical system. Once the current i_s and the gas column voltage V_{gc} are known, the energy release to the gas phase is computed as follows:

$$\dot{Q}_{spk}(t) = V_{gc}(t) \cdot i_s(t) \quad (5.3.16)$$

The experiments from Herweg and Maly [44] illustrate that the flow field in the vicinity of the spark plug significantly affects η_{eff} during both arc and glow discharge processes. In particular, when the discharge channel is elongated by the flow field, the ratio of the column voltage V_{gc} to the anode and cathode voltage falls increase and the heat losses to

the electrodes decrease. Hence, the correlation proposed in [44] is employed in the model. The restrike is assumed to take place every time the gas column voltage becomes higher than the threshold value. In the proposed approach, when the restrike occurs, a new set of particles is placed along the spark gap. The old particles continue to evolve inside the computational domain, but they lose the corresponding heat term in the energy equation.

Figure 5.4: Plasma channel formation and evolution (a–c); restrike (d) and flame surface density calculation (e) [58].

Flame surface density calculation

Once the particles are tracked in the computational mesh, it is necessary to reconstruct the flame surface density distribution resulting from the size and position of the particles. To perform this operation a spherical triangulated surface is placed at any particle location. Then the radius of each sphere is adjusted to match the value of the representative particle. The flame surface is defined by the total amount of non-intersecting triangles of the placed spheres. The number of triangular faces N_f belonging to each computational cell is identified and the flame surface density Σ is computed for each cell as:

$$\Sigma_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N A_i}{V_{cell}} \quad (5.3.17)$$

where A_i is the area of each triangle. An insight into how the flame surface density is computed is provided in Fig. 5.4. Distribution of Σ_k is then used to estimate the reaction

rate source term in the progress variable equation, according to the flame surface density formulation. When one of the kernels radii reaches a threshold value (2 mm [52]), the combustion model switches to the complete Eulerian description and both the progress variable and the Σ equations are solved. The Σ field is initialized with the profile provided by the described method. The coupling between the Eulerian gas phase and the Lagrangian ignition model is only done through the flame surface density distribution, while the energy from the electrical circuit is not transferred to the ambient gas, but only to the Lagrangian particles. This choice was mainly motivated by the complexity that is required to compute chemical equilibrium and gas properties in 5000–50000 K range, accounting for the proper species composition in the burned gases.

5.4 Direct Energy Deposition Model

Up to this point in the chapter several ignition models for 3D CFD engine simulations based on the sub-grid modeling with use of the Lagrangian particles have been reviewed. These models were developed to overcome the requirement of a very fine mesh around the spark plug to fully resolve the spark discharge process. The recent increase in the computational power of high performance computers encouraged researchers to adopt finer computational meshes to resolve the onset of spark ignition in the combustion simulations [60–62]. Such ignition modeling in the pure Eulerian domain appears to be more intuitive, as the sole input is reduced to an energy source term added to the energy equation of the fluid solver. Authors of [60–62] used the CONVERGE CFD code to simulate combustion through the detailed chemistry with reaction rates defined in Arrhenius-type constants. This approach is necessary for application of the Direct Energy Deposition Model (DEDM), since it can predict the ignition of the mixture due to the heat input into the computational cells. Yang et al. [60] considered combustion of gasoline and used a Primary Reference Fuel (PRF) mechanism [63] for combustion modeling, Scarcelli et al. in [61] considered lean burning gasoline but used a different chemical scheme [64] and Zhang et al. in [62] investigated lean and dilute methane/air mixtures with GRI mechanism [65]. The energy source for the DEDM model is either defined based on the measurement from the real ignition system or calculated with an electrical circuit model. In engine cases simulated in [60,61] the energy from the electrical circuit is deposited into

the spherical volume between the spark electrodes. This means that the DEDM model in these cases completely omits the spark channel modeling, its interaction with the flow field and influence on the ignition process. Zhang et al. [62] consider an academic example with energy deposition into the square channel between the electrodes and compare it to the spherical ignition source used previously. They also make a validation of their simulations in regard to the optical ignition measurements of the lean and dilute methane/air mixtures to conclude that the line-shaped energy source geometry is closer in nature to the electrical discharge and superior to the spherical geometry in energy distribution and the flame kernel shape prediction. Although the application of the DEDM model in presented cases provided satisfactory results for the authors, it seems to be not suitable for engine cases, where spark channel is expected to distort significantly due to the high tumble or interaction with the spray. The spark channel monitoring models reviewed in section 5.3 should be much more accurate in spark ignition simulations with high velocity flow fields.

Chapter 6

Development and implementation of a new and comprehensive Spark Ignition model

The literature review on the ignition models for 3D CFD combustion modeling in SI engines in Chapter 5 has shown that in each model particular aspects of the ignition phenomenon are accurately described while others are taken into account in a simplified manner, or even completely omitted. The aim of this work is to propose a comprehensive and predictive ignition model, which provides for all aspects of the spark ignition process that have influence on the early flame kernel formation, growth and transition to the combustion model. The model proposed in this thesis has been implemented into AVL Fire™ 3D CFD solver and combined with the G -equation combustion model for the turbulent flame propagation. The required input from the user is information on the engine ignition system, such as inductance (L_s), resistance (R_s) and energy stored in the secondary ignition circuit. Additionally, the spark plug geometry needs to be included in the 3D CFD mesh.

The detailed description of the mixture inflammation by the spark discharge is given in Chapter 3. Here, the basics of the spark ignition are briefly summarized as a ground for the ignition model. During the breakdown phase of the ignition process, the thin, cylindrical plasma channel is formed between the electrodes. The temperature and pressure of this channel rises very rapidly up to values of 60000 K and several hundred atmospheres. Most of the breakdown plasma energy is transferred to the surrounding gas within the small

cylindrical volume into which the breakdown plasma expands. The breakdown phase is always followed by the arc and glow phases during which the plasma energy is further transferred into the surrounding gas. Due to the energy transfer the temperature in the spark channel lowers to about 6000 K during the arc phase and 3500 K during the glow phase. Since the plasma temperatures are much too high to allow the species present in the normal combustion products to exist, combustion reactions take place at the outer plasma surface where the conditions are ideal for rapid chemical activity (temperatures of one thousand to a few thousand Kelvins) [1, 2]. This is the main assumption for the proposed ignition model. The main parts of the model are the spark channel dynamics, the electrical circuit and the solution of the 1D heat equation in the normal direction to the spark channel surface to obtain the temperature at the surface of the plasma channel and the corresponding ignition delay time.

The proposed ignition model is comprised of five different submodels: the spark channel submodel, the electrical circuit submodel, the temperature diffusion submodel, ignition delay submodel and the initial kernel growth submodel. In the first submodel the spark channel is represented by a set of Lagrangian particles which movement is calculated based on the velocity interpolated from a cell-centered value in the 3D domain. Additionally, a special scheme for the curve movement is incorporated in order to obtain even distribution of moving particles along the spark channel and a correct calculation of the spark channel curvature. The details of this submodel are described in section 6.1. During the spark movement the electrical circuit and the ignition delay submodels are solved simultaneously. The result of the electrical circuit model is the heat transferred to the plasma channel and its surroundings. In the temperature diffusion submodel the heat diffusion from the spark channel towards the surrounding mixture is calculated. Based on the solution of the 1D heat equation with curvature terms, the temperature at the surface of the spark is calculated for every particle. Then, in the ignition delay submodel all necessary properties of the mixture are interpolated from the 3D domain and the Ignition Delay Time (IDT) for these properties at the temperature of the spark surface is obtained from the tabulated values. For an instantaneous value of the ignition delay time, a precursor of ignition is calculated. The ignition occurs for the computational particle of the spark channel at which the value of 1.0 is first reached by the precursor. The details of these submodels are given in sections 6.2, 6.3 and 6.4. As soon as the ignition of the mixture

takes place, the initial flame kernel is introduced at the calculated position along the spark channel. If the 3D mesh resolution is fine enough to resolve the surface of the kernel, the flame propagation is handled by the G -equation combustion model. Otherwise, the early stage of kernel growth is handled by the growth model described in section 6.5. When kernel becomes large enough to be solved on the 3D mesh, a transition from the growth model to the combustion model is performed. From this stage on, the flame propagation is handled by the G -equation combustion model.

6.1 Modeling of the spark channel dynamics

The purpose of this submodel is a proper description of the spark channel dynamics and its deflection during the 3D engine simulation. The visible channel that is formed between the spark electrodes as a result of breakdown is a hot plasma consisting of gas atoms, ions and molecules. The local flow field around the spark plug can drag this plasma channel and significantly change its shape and length. Since the representation of the cylindrical shape of the channel on the standard 3D engine mesh is not possible, the spark channel in this model is considered as an evolving 3D curve represented by discrete Lagrangian particles $\mathbf{r}_i^n = (x_i^n, y_i^n, z_i^n)$, where $i = 0, \dots, m$, denotes the particle number and n , the discrete time stepping. An example of the spark channel represented by particles is given in 6.1. The velocity vector field \mathbf{v} for the curve movement is interpolated from the cell-centered value of the 3D mesh for each particle. The basic model for the movement of particles can be given by $\partial_t \mathbf{r} = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{r})$, which means that particles move independently of each other. Depending on the velocity field, this type of movement can lead to self-intersections and irregular distances between the particles which would finally affect the calculation of the local curvature. At this point it should be noted that the correct curvature calculation is of high importance for the calculation of the temperature at the surface of the spark channel described in section 6.3.

In order to overcome the shortcomings of the simple movement model, an advanced scheme for curve movement proposed by Mikula et al. [66–68] is implemented. This scheme assures the smooth shape of the moving curve thanks to particles redistribution and curvature regularization performed during the movement. It is based on the fact that the motion of the curve can be decomposed into the tangential and normal direction and the

Figure 6.1: Spark channel represented by 50 Lagrangian particles.

overall shape of the evolving curve with the fixed end points is determined only by the normal component of the velocity. The tangential component of the velocity influences only the distribution of the points along the curve that they represent. If the tangential movement of the points is not controlled, it can cause accumulation of the points which would lead to the problems mentioned previously. Hence, it is necessary to control the tangential movement of the points during the curve evolution. Taking all of it into consideration, the regularized motion of the curve can be described as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial t} = \mu \mathbf{N}_{\mathbf{v}} + \epsilon k \mathbf{N} + \alpha \mathbf{T} \quad (6.1.1)$$

where $\mathbf{N}_{\mathbf{v}}$ is the projection of the velocity vector field \mathbf{v} to the curve normal plane, $k\mathbf{N}$ is the curvature vector, which is in the curve normal plane and \mathbf{T} is the unit tangent vector to the curve. Parameters μ , ϵ are responsible for the particle movement in the normal direction and for the curvature regularization. The last parameter α is the tangential velocity which controls the particles distribution.

The final model is given in the form of the following intrinsic advection-diffusion PDE with a driving force:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial t} = \mu \mathbf{N}_{\mathbf{v}} + \epsilon \frac{\partial^2 \mathbf{r}}{\partial s^2} + \alpha \frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial s} \quad (6.1.2)$$

which is discretized by the flowing finite volume method [66]. The derivation of the tangential velocity α that assures the uniform distribution of particles during the curve evolution is given in [68]. The final result of the movement scheme is smooth curve motion with a uniform distribution of particles.

Figure 6.2: Comparison of the particles movement without (left) and with (right) redistribution.

A comparison between the simple movement and the movement with the curvature regularization and particles redistribution is given in Fig. 6.2 for a spark channel represented by 100 particles. Irregular distances between the particles are clearly visible in case of the simple movement. Furthermore, the curvature calculation might be affected by an accumulation of particles in the region of high curvature which manifests itself as considerably higher local curvature value for a single particle. On the other hand, the result obtained with the advanced movement scheme shows even distribution of particles along the spark channel and smooth shape of the curve corresponding to a smooth changes in the curvature.

6.2 Modeling of the secondary electrical circuit

A classical inductive ignition system comprises the primary and secondary circuits. In the electrical circuit submodel the current in the secondary circuit i_s and the voltage of the spark gas column V_{gc} are calculated in order to estimate the heat delivered to the spark channel. A simplified scheme of the ignition system has already been given in section 3.1. The primary circuit includes the battery, the switch, the primary resistance R_p and the primary inductance L_p . The secondary circuit includes the secondary resistance, the secondary inductance and the spark plug. During the ignition process only about 60% of the energy stored in the primary inductance is transferred to the spark plug, the rest of it being dissipated by the secondary inductance L_s . In the presented model only the secondary part of the circuit is represented similarly as in [11]. The energy available in the secondary circuit E_s is given as an input parameter, as well as the other properties of the

electrical circuit (the secondary inductance L_s and the secondary resistance R_s). During the first few μs the voltage rise between electrodes is calculated. The spark deposition takes place when the voltage reaches the breakdown voltage. The breakdown voltage is calculated based on the Paschen's law [6] with a temperature correction [69] as follows:

$$V_{bd} = \frac{B_0 p d_{ie} \frac{T}{T_0}}{\ln \left(A'_0 p d_{ie} \frac{T}{T_0} \right)} \quad (6.2.1)$$

where $T_0 = 295$ K, $B_0 = 380$ V \cdot Torr $^{-1}$ \cdot cm $^{-1}$ [70], $A'_0 = 2.9$ Torr $^{-1}$ \cdot cm $^{-1}$ [70], T is temperature in K, p is pressure in Torr and d_{ie} is inter-electrode distance in cm.

The following phases of the spark process are arc and glow phase. During these phases, the current in the secondary circuit is given by the relation:

$$i_s = \sqrt{\frac{2E_s}{L_s}} \quad (6.2.2)$$

and the voltage between the electrodes V_{ie} is calculated as:

$$V_{ie} = V_{cf} + V_{af} + V_{gc} \quad (6.2.3)$$

where V_{cf} and V_{af} are the cathode and anode voltage falls given by Kim et al. [10]. V_{gc} is the voltage of gas column along the spark channel and its calculation depends on the ignition mode. Kim et al. [10] suggest, that when the current level i_s is above 60 mA, the arc mode should be assumed and the voltage V_{gc} is calculated as:

$$V_{gc} = 6.31 \cdot l_{spark} i_s^{-0.75} p^{0.51} \quad (6.2.4)$$

while for current level i_s below 60 mA, the glow mode is valid and voltage V_{gc} is given by:

$$V_{gc} = 40.46 \cdot l_{spark} i_s^{-0.32} p^{0.51} \quad (6.2.5)$$

With the calculated current i_s in the secondary circuit and the voltage along the spark channel, the energy transfer to the hot plasma column is calculated as:

$$\dot{Q}_{gc} = V_{gc} \cdot i_s \quad (6.2.6)$$

During the spark discharge, the electrical energy available in the secondary circuit is constantly reduced. The decrease in E_s is given by:

$$\frac{dE_s(t)}{dt} = -R_s i_s^2(t) - V_{ie} i_s(t) \quad (6.2.7)$$

The glow phase lasts as long as $V_{ie} < V_{bd}$. When inter-electrode voltage reaches the breakdown voltage, a restrike takes place. The current spark channel disappears and a new one is formed between the electrodes. Depending on the energy available in the secondary circuit, several restrikes can happen during the single spark discharge event. The spark discharge process lasts as long as there is energy available in the secondary circuit of the ignition system $E_s(t) > 0$.

6.3 Modeling of the temperature diffusion

In case of a homogeneous combustion process in SI engine, no steep gradients in temperature and mixture composition can be found in the combustion chamber at the time of ignition. If one assumes that ignition delay time during the spark ignition process depends on the local temperature, pressure and mixture fraction only, a simultaneous ignition along the entire spark channel should occur. However, recent experimental studies on ignition process in SI engines show that only a single flame kernel develops at the specific location along the spark channel [8,9,24]. These observations lead to the conclusion that additional effects influence the spark ignition process and the formation of the flame kernel. According to Schaefer [8] the deflection of the spark channel has an effect on the heat transfer and species diffusion in the normal direction to the plasma surface. The curvature of the spark channel leads to an increased or reduced local energy transfer depending on a convex or concave shape. To account for the diffusion processes under the influence of curvature Schaefer [8] solved governing equations for temperature, species transport and chemical reaction rates at the spark channel surface.

In the current work a similar approach as in [8,57] is incorporated. For simplification only the governing equation for temperature is solved in the normal direction to the spark surface. The ignition delay time is obtained from tabulated values based on the temperature calculated at the spark channel surface, pressure and local composition of the mixture. The derivation of the temperature equation with curvature terms starts

from the geometrical definition of the constant diameter spark channel surface $K(x, t)$. The kinematics of this surface can be described with the following transport equation:

$$\frac{d}{dt}K(x, t) = \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} + \frac{d\mathbf{x}_f}{dt} \quad (6.3.1)$$

where the velocity of the spark channel is given by the local flow field \mathbf{v}_α :

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_f}{dt} = \mathbf{v}_\alpha \quad (6.3.2)$$

With assumption of the constant spark channel diameter with no self-induced dynamics, the transport equation finally reads:

$$\frac{\partial K}{\partial t} + v_\alpha \cdot \nabla K = 0 \quad (6.3.3)$$

where $\frac{\partial K}{\partial t}$ accounts for the temporal change and $v_\alpha \cdot \nabla K$ for the convective change of the iso-surface K .

The transient governing equation for the temperature is solved at the spark channel surface K and reads:

$$\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \rho u_i \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} \right) - \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial x_i} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_i} - \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} + \dot{Q}_{in} = 0 \quad (6.3.4)$$

where u_i is the velocity component in the x_i direction of the Cartesian coordinate system, λ is the thermal conductivity, c_p is the heat capacity, p is the pressure and \dot{Q}_{in} is the heat source.

Since the heat transfer from the spark channel to the surrounding gas occurs mainly in the normal direction to the plasma surface, the temperature equation should be solved in the normal direction to the K -surface. By introducing the normal vector to the K -surface:

$$\mathbf{n}_K = - \frac{\nabla K}{|\nabla K|} \quad (6.3.5)$$

the curvature κ of the K -surface can be described as:

$$\kappa_K = \nabla \cdot \mathbf{n}_K = \frac{\nabla^2 K - \mathbf{n}_K \cdot \nabla(\mathbf{n}_K \cdot \nabla K)}{|\nabla K|} \quad (6.3.6)$$

Then, the coordinate system can be transformed in such a way that the coordinate x_1 is

Figure 6.3: K -coordinate system on the spark channel surface [8].

normal to the K -surface. The new K -coordinate system on the spark channel surface is presented in Fig. 6.3. With the coordinate system transformation, the curvature becomes:

$$\kappa_K = \frac{\left(\frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_i^2} - \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_1^2} \right)}{|\nabla K|} = - \frac{\sum_{\beta=2}^3 \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_\beta^2}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_i} \right)^2}} \quad (6.3.7)$$

Furthermore, rotating x_1 to the normal direction of the K -surface the new coordinate system is defined as:

$$K_1 = K(x_1, x_2, x_3, t), \quad K_2 = x_2, \quad K_3 = x_3, \quad \tau = t \quad (6.3.8)$$

Since K_2 is independent of x_1 and x_3 while K_3 is independent of x_1 and x_2 , the transformation rules are:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} \frac{\partial}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} \quad (6.3.9)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \quad (6.3.10)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} = \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial}{\partial K_\beta}, \quad \beta = 2, 3 \quad (6.3.11)$$

With this transformation the unsteady term in (6.3.4) reads:

$$\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \rho \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} \quad (6.3.12)$$

The convective term in the x_1 direction is:

$$\rho u_1 \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_1} = \rho u_1 \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \quad (6.3.13)$$

and in the x_β direction:

$$\rho u_\beta \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} = \rho u_\beta \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta} \right) \quad (6.3.14)$$

The thermal conduction term in the x_1 direction is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_1} \right) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial K^2} = \\ &= \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_1^2} \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial K^2} \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.15)$$

and in the x_β direction:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} \right) &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_\beta^2} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.16)$$

The thermal conduction due to heat capacity changes in the x_1 direction is:

$$\frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \quad (6.3.17)$$

and in the x_β direction:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta} &= \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K_\beta} \right) \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta} \right) = \\ &= \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \left[\left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \right)^2 \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta} + \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K_\beta} + \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.18)$$

For further simplification it is assumed that the temperature gradients tangential to the spark channel surface (in x_β direction) are small compared to the gradients normal (in x_1 direction) to the surface. According to [71, 72] it is possible to assume that gradients (but

not necessarily the second derivatives) in the tangential direction are negligible:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \approx 0, \quad \frac{\partial}{\partial K_\beta} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} - \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \approx 0, \quad \beta = 2, 3 \quad (6.3.19)$$

With equation (6.3.19) the thermal conduction in the x_β direction (6.3.16) is simplified to:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x_\beta} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial x_\beta}}_{\approx 0} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_\beta^2} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \approx \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_\beta^2} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \quad (6.3.20)$$

The thermal conduction due to the heat capacity changes in the x_β direction (6.3.18) is simplified with equation (6.3.19) to:

$$\frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \left[\underbrace{\left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \right)^2}_{\approx 0} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta}}_{\approx 0} + \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \underbrace{\frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K_\beta}}_{\approx 0} + \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K_\beta} \underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta}}_{\approx 0} \right] \approx 0 \quad (6.3.21)$$

Combining transformed unsteady (6.3.12) and convective (6.3.13, 6.3.14) terms with the K -surface transport equation (6.3.3) and equation (6.3.19) gives:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} + \rho u_1 \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \rho u_\beta \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \underbrace{\frac{\partial T}{\partial K_\beta}}_{\approx 0} \right) = \\ = \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} + \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \underbrace{\left(\rho \frac{\partial K}{\partial t} + \rho u_1 \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} + \rho u_\beta \frac{\partial K}{\partial x_\beta} \right)}_{=0} = \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial \tau} \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.22)$$

Finally, adding all transformed terms, the temperature equation reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_1^2} \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \right) \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial K^2} + \\ + \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial^2 K}{\partial x_\beta^2} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \left(\frac{\partial K}{\partial x_1} \right)^2 \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.23)$$

With $|\nabla K| = 1$ and the curvature definition from equation (6.3.7) the temperature equation in the final form reads:

$$\rho \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial}{\partial K} \left(\frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \right) - \kappa_\beta \frac{\lambda}{c_p} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{\lambda}{c_p^2} \frac{\partial c_p}{\partial K} \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} + \frac{1}{c_p} \frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \quad (6.3.24)$$

where κ_β is the sum of curvatures in the tangential directions:

$$\kappa_\beta = \kappa_2 + \kappa_3 \quad (6.3.25)$$

Relating the curvature κ_β to Fig. 6.3, the curvature κ_2 in the K_2 direction describes the curvature caused by the spark channel deflection. For simplification it is calculated as the curvature of the curve representing the spark channel at the given point and it is assumed that any deflection of the spark channel corresponds to the concave shape and the negative sign of the curvature κ_2 . The curvature κ_3 in the K_3 direction is caused by the cylindrical geometry of the spark channel, having the convex shape and the positive sign with the value of $\kappa_3 = 1/r$.

The governing temperature equation in the final form is a 1D heat equation which can be easily discretized with the Finite Difference Method. The first grid point of the K -domain is located at the spark channel surface. In order to solve this equation firstly, the temperature along the K -domain T_{ini} is initialized with the temperature interpolated from the 3D domain for the given spark particle. Since the temperature diffusion is calculated normal to the spark channel surface towards the unburnt mixture, one of the boundary conditions represents the heat input from the spark channel, while the other the properties of the mixture in the vicinity of the spark plug. The heat transfer from the spark towards

Figure 6.4: Setup and an exemplary result of the solution of the 1D heat equation.

the K -domain is described with the *Neumann* boundary condition as the temperature gradient at the surface of the spark channel:

$$\left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial K} \right|_{K=0} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{el} \cdot \eta_{eff}}{\lambda \cdot A_{spk}} \quad (6.3.26)$$

where \dot{Q}_{el} is the power supplied from the electric circuit to the spark channel, η_{eff} is the efficiency of the heat transfer from the spark plasma to the surrounding mixture and A_{spk} is the area of the spark channel surface. Based on experimental measurements from [44] and [13] values of $\eta_{eff} = 0.2$ for the arc phase and $\eta_{eff} = 0.09$ for the glow phase are adopted. The boundary condition at the n^{th} point of the K -domain is the constant temperature condition corresponding to the temperature of the mixture in the vicinity of the spark (interpolated from cell-centered value).

$$T|_{K=n} = T_{unb} \quad (6.3.27)$$

With time advance the temperature at the first grid point of the K -domain is increased due to the temperature gradient. Simultaneously, the temperature diffusion process towards the unburnt mixture counteracts the temperature increase and a specific temperature profile is obtained over the K -domain. The highest temperature is at the spark surface ($K = 0$) and ignition is expected to take place there. The setup and an exemplary profile of the temperature is given in Fig. 6.4. The equation is solved for each particle representing the spark channel. The temperature at the spark surface ($K = 0$) is of particular importance, since it is the highest temperature in the K -domain and the ignition is expected to take place there. Hence, only the history of temperature at the first grid point of the K -domain for each particle of the spark channel is necessary for the ignition delay time calculation. An example result of the temperature calculated at the spark channel surface is given in Fig. 6.5.

6.4 Modeling of the ignition delay

In the current work only the temperature equation derived in the previous section is solved in the normal direction to the spark channel surface. Since there is no governing equation for species transport, it is not possible to determine the ignition timing with a

Figure 6.5: Example of the temperature calculated at the surface of the spark channel at the ignition time.

kinetic oxidation scheme. Instead, the ignition delay after the spark deposition is calculated based on the tabulated values of IDTs for given mixture composition and properties. The convenience of this approach comes from the fact that there is no need of solving the species transport equation and tabulated IDTs for several different fuels are already available in the AVL FireTM database. It means that the ignition model described in this study and implemented in the AVL FireTM software can be used for any fuel that is included in the AVL FireTM database. The IDTs are tabulated as a function of temperature, pressure, equivalence ratio and residual gas fraction $\tau(T, p, \phi, \text{EGR})$.

Since the temperature of the spark channel and mixture properties in the vicinity of the spark plug are changing in time, it is necessary to provide a model that will account for these changes and correctly predict the ignition based on the tabulated IDTs. For this purpose a model for knock prediction proposed in [73] is adapted for calculating the delay between the spark deposition and the appearance of the first flame kernel. Firstly, a precursor of ignition is introduced for each particle of the spark channel. At every time step all values needed for reading the IDTs from the table are collected. As regards temperature input, the temperature calculated at the first grid point of the K -domain (at spark channel surface) for given particle is taken. Pressure, equivalence ratio and residual gas fraction are interpolated from the 3D domain for each particle. With these values the IDT is read from the table. Knowing an instantaneous IDT for each particle representing the spark channel, a change of precursor Y_p is calculated as follows:

$$\frac{dY_p}{dt} = \frac{\sqrt{\alpha^2 \tau^2 + 4(1 - \alpha\tau)Y_p}}{\tau} \quad (6.4.1)$$

where α is the model constant set to 1.0 and τ is the instantaneous ignition delay time at given conditions. Ignition occurs when the precursor reaches value of 1.0.

In order to evaluate if the model for precursor correctly predicts the ignition delay time, a comparison of ignition delay calculation with the precursor model based on the AVL FireTM IDT database and with a detailed kinetic scheme is performed and presented in Fig. 6.6. The AVL FireTM IDT database covers various transportation fuels and provides IDTs for auto-ignition relevant conditions. The following comparison is performed for two fuels — methane (which is the main component of the natural gas burned in gas engines) and Primary Reference Fuel (PRF95, which is a gasoline surrogate composed of 95% iso-octane and 5% n-heptane). As for the conditions, the comparison is performed for a stoichiometric mixtures ($\phi = 1.0$) without EGR, for temperatures from 900 K to 1600 K for methane and from 700 K to 1500 K for PRF95, for pressures from 10 bar to 100 bar for methane and from 5 bar to 80 bar for PRF95. The ignition delay time calculations with a detailed kinetic scheme are performed in a constant volume reactor with adaptive time step in Cantera software. The calculation of IDTs of methane is done with the GRI-mech 3.0 [65] kinetic mechanism that consists of 53 species and 325 reactions. The calculation of IDTs of PRF95 is done with the reduced mechanism for gasoline surrogates [74] that consists of 156 species and 3370 reactions. The comparison for methane presented in Fig. 6.6 shows very good agreement in ignition delay times between the precursor model and the kinetic scheme in all range of investigated conditions. These results allow to draw two main conclusions. Firstly, the AVL FireTM IDT database for methane is most probably created based on the GRI mechanism. Secondly, the good agreement in ignition delay times confirms that the precursor model provides correct results and can be used for prediction of the ignition delay times based on the provided database. On the other hand, the comparison of IDTs for the PRF95 fuel gives more differences between the precursor model and the kinetic mechanism, especially in the region of low temperatures, known as the Negative Temperature Coefficient (NTC) region. The NTC region is characteristic for higher hydrocarbons and reveals itself as an inflection on a logarithmic graph of the ignition delay times below 1000 K. The study of ignition delay times in the NTC region is a challenging task and a number of kinetic schemes for different fuels that account for this region has been developed over the years. The results obtained in the comparison suggest that a different kinetic scheme must have been used for building the database

for PRF95 fuel in the AVL FireTM software. Furthermore, fairly good agreement in the ignition delay times of PRF95 fuel for high temperatures (above 1000 K) again confirms that the precursor model is capable of a correct prediction of the ignition delay times and its accuracy is dependent only on the provided IDT database.

Figure 6.6: Ignition delay times calculated with the precursor based on the AVL FireTM IDT database and with a detailed kinetic scheme. Results for CH₄ (left) and PRF (right).

Figure 6.7: Example of the precursor result on the particles at the ignition time.

Calculating the precursor with the model presented in this section allows to account for the history of changes in the mixture composition, pressure and temperature. It is important especially for changes in temperature caused by the heat transfer from the spark channel to the surrounding mixture. The difference in the curvature between particles affects the temperature calculated at the spark channel surface which has an impact on

the precursor and the final position of the ignition point. It is expected that the ignition should take place in a region of high curvature due to an increased temperature. Finally, the precursor for each particle representing the spark channel is obtained for a given time.

6.5 Initial flame kernel growth and transition to the combustion model

When the ignition timing and position are calculated, a spherical flame kernel is initiated (0.5 mm [9, 15]). With a mesh refined to an element size of approximately 0.1 mm in the vicinity of the ignition point it is possible to resolve the initial flame kernel surface and calculate the flame propagation with the G -equation model from the beginning of kernel growth. However, for a coarser engine meshes the initial kernel growth should be calculated with a 0D model until the surface of the flame can be resolved on the numerical mesh. The expansion speed of the kernel is calculated as:

$$\frac{dr_K}{dt} = \frac{\rho_u}{\rho_b} s_K \quad (6.5.1)$$

where ρ_u and ρ_b are burned and unburned densities and s_K is the burning velocity at the surface of the kernel calculated by:

$$s_K = \max(s_L, s_T - \frac{2}{r_K} D_t) \quad (6.5.2)$$

The laminar burning velocity s_L is read from the AVL FireTM database for the given mixture composition and properties, while the turbulent flame speed s_T is calculated as:

$$s_T = s_L(1 + \sigma_t) \quad (6.5.3)$$

where σ_t can be calculated with one of the two available correlations — correlation proposed by Peters [3] for a fully developed turbulent flame or correlation proposed by Ewald [75] accounting for unsteady effects during the flame development. The turbulent diffusivity D_t which considers the influence of the turbulence on the small flame kernels is calculated accordingly to the correlation chosen for the turbulent flame speed. During the flame kernel growth, the G -scalar is computed by enforcing a spherical distribution

Figure 6.8: Initial flame kernel in the calculated position and time.

with G_0 located at the distance r_K from the ignition point:

$$G(x, y, z) = r_K(t) - \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \quad (6.5.4)$$

As soon as the flame kernel is large enough to resolve its surface on the computational grid the transition from the spark ignition model to the combustion model takes place. From this point on the flame propagation is calculated with the G -equation for RANS engine simulations [3], which is numerically solved by the semi-implicit level set method with inflow-based gradient [76, 77]. For the G -equation combustion model, an initialization of the G -scalar is necessary by enforcing a spherical distribution with G_0 located at a kernel radius distance from the ignition point.

6.6 Possibility of a misfire

A comprehensive description of the spark-ignition process given in sections 6.1–6.5 allows to predict a misfire of the air-fuel mixture. The misfire happens when the spark discharge does not result in a successful flame kernel initialization and the following flame propagation. In this work three mechanisms leading to the misfire are considered and included in the model. Firstly, the misfire can happen whenever the precursor introduced in section 6.4 does not reach the ignition threshold. This can take place when the ignition delay of the air-fuel mixture is longer than the duration of the spark discharge. In case of a very lean or very rich mixture which is outside the flammability limits, the ignition delay approaches infinity and the model predicts misfire. In case of a mixture within

the flammability limits a strong flow field at the spark plug may reduce the period for supplying discharge energy to the mixture by blowing off the spark channel and causing multiple spark breakdowns during a single discharge event [22]. When the ignition delay of the mixture is longer than the duration of the single spark breakdown under the strong flow field, the model predicts the misfire. The second mechanism of the misfire is based on the Karlovitz number as described in [22] and [24]. Even if the precursor reaches the ignition threshold predicting a localized ignition event it does not have to lead to the successful flame propagation. If the Kolmogorov eddies break both the diffusion and the reaction zones of a flame kernel under local mixture conditions, the flame structure cannot be preserved leading to an extinction of the flame kernel (the *broken reaction zone* regime of the premixed turbulent combustion described in section 4.4). Therefore, a local Karlovitz number Ka_δ (Eq. 4.4.9) is calculated for each particle representing the spark channel, serving as a criterion for successful ignition. If the *broken reaction zone* regime is identified for a spark channel particle, the model predicts the misfire for this particle even though the precursor can indicate an ignition. When the local criteria of the precursor and the Karlovitz number are fulfilled for any particle of the spark channel, an ignition takes place and a flame kernel is introduced in the computational domain. This flame kernel can still be quenched due to local flame-wall interactions leading to the misfire. Hence, the third mechanism of the misfire is included not in the presented ignition model itself but in the G -equation combustion model, which considers a detailed description of the flame-wall interactions. Finally, a successful ignition and flame propagation are possible only when the local criteria of the precursor and the Karlovitz number are fulfilled and the flame kernel is not quenched during the initial phase of its growth.

6.7 Influence of the model parameters on the ignition process

The proposed model describes several physical processes that are of importance for spark ignition in IC engines. The ignition delay calculated with the model accounts for the properties of the electrical circuit, properties of the mixture (pressure, temperature, equivalence ratio and EGR), shape of the spark channel (curvature of the surface) and efficiency of the heat transfer from the spark channel towards surrounding mixture. In

order to give an overview of the influence of individual parameters on the ignition delay, a series of 1D calculations with the proposed model is performed and discussed in this section. The setup of the 1D case is presented in Fig. 6.4 and a summary of investigated conditions is given in Table 6.1.

Table 6.1: Conditions investigated in the 1D case.

Parameter	Base value	Investigated range
Unburned temperature	600 K	const.
Spark channel length	1 mm	const.
Pressure	10 bar	5 – 50 bar
Equivalence ratio	1.0	0.5 – 1.5
Initial electrical energy	40 mJ	20 – 120 mJ
Heat transfer efficiency	0.10	0.05 – 0.30
Radius of the spark channel	50 μm	10 – 100 μm
Curvature of the spark channel	20000 1/m	10000 – 30000 1/m

The influence of the pressure and equivalence ratio on the ignition delay calculated with the model is presented in Fig. 6.9. It can be observed that with pressure increase, the ignition delay is longer. An increased density of the gas with the assumption of the same heat source gives lower temperatures. Together with an increased thermal conductivity for higher pressures, the temperature gradient at the spark channel is lower (Eq. 6.3.26) leading to lower temperatures and a longer ignition delay. On the other hand, there is a correlation between the pressure and the gas column voltage (Eqs. 6.2.4 and 6.2.5). A higher pressure requires a higher voltage along the spark channel, which corresponds to the higher heat input that should lead to higher temperatures and shorter ignition delay times. Also the chemistry of the fuel has an impact on the ignition delay — shorter ignition delays are observed for higher pressures. The overall effect of the pressure depends on all three factors that have been mentioned and the first one appears to have the most influence leading to a longer ignition delay for higher pressures. As for the equivalence ratio, the chemistry of the fuel has the most impact on the ignition delay leading to longer delays for higher equivalence ratios within the flammable region, as shown in Fig. 6.9.

Figure 6.10 presents the influence of the radius of the spark channel and the curvature of the spark surface on the ignition delay. With a larger radius, the cylindrical curvature of the spark channel surface (κ_3 in Fig. 6.3) is smaller. The smaller curvature of the convex shape leads to a decreased heat diffusion in the normal direction, higher temperatures at the surface and a shorter ignition delay. However, with an increase of the radius, the larger area of the surface contributes to lower temperature gradients at the surface of the

Figure 6.9: Influence of the pressure (left) and the equivalence ratio (right) on the ignition delay.

plasma (Eq. 6.3.26) finally leading to lower temperatures and a longer ignition delay. The overall curvature of the spark surface consists of the curvature κ_2 caused by the spark channel deflection and the curvature κ_3 corresponding to the cylindrical geometry of the channel. With the fixed radius and κ_3 , the curvature κ_2 can influence the heat transfer in two ways. If the deflection of the channel results in a concave geometry of the surface, the curvature κ_2 is negative and the overall curvature of the surface $\kappa_2 + \kappa_3$ is reduced leading to a decreased heat diffusion in the normal direction, higher temperatures at the surface and a shorter ignition delay. If the deflection of the channel results in a convex geometry of the surface, the curvature κ_2 is positive and the overall curvature of the surface $\kappa_2 + \kappa_3$ is increased leading to an increased heat diffusion in the normal direction, lower temperatures at the surface and a longer ignition delay. Since the proposed model is to predict the earliest ignition point, the curvature κ_2 is assumed to always correspond to the concave shape of the surface of the spark channel contributing to a shorter ignition delay at any deflection of the spark channel.

Figure 6.10: Influence of the radius of the spark channel (left) and the curvature of the spark channel surface (right) on the ignition delay.

Figure 6.11: Influence of the initial energy in the secondary electrical circuit (left) and the efficiency of the heat transfer towards the unburned mixture (right) on the ignition delay.

The influence of the initial energy available in the secondary electrical circuit and the efficiency of the heat transfer is given in Fig. 6.11. Based on Eq. 6.2.2 the larger amount of the energy in the electrical circuit increases the current in the circuit, which corresponds to a higher heat input, higher temperature gradients and temperatures, finally shortening the ignition delay. As for the efficiency of the heat transfer from the spark channel towards unburned mixture, from Eq. 6.3.26 higher efficiency leads to increased temperature gradients and temperatures at the spark surface, eventually contributing to shorter ignition delay.

6.8 Influence of the mesh resolution on the ignition position and delay time

The new ignition model is developed to be used for 3D CFD combustion modeling in SI engines. Hence, it is necessary to investigate how the mesh resolution influences the results obtained with the ignition model. To that end, an academic case is set up, which includes a constant volume chamber of a cylindrical shape with a spark plug placed at the cylinder wall. The purpose of this setup is only to initialize a swirl motion inside the cylinder to generate the desired velocity at the spark plug. Three different refinements of the mesh at the spark plug are investigated and shown in Fig. 6.12. In the fine mesh, the elements at the spark gap are refined to the size of 0.05 mm, in the medium mesh to 0.1 mm and in the coarse mesh to 0.2 mm. In the chamber a stoichiometric mixture of gasoline under the pressure of 10 bar and the temperature of 400 K is initialized. The initialized swirl motion is adjusted to obtain the velocity of the magnitude of the order

of 15 m/s at the gap of the spark plug. According to [23] the velocities of the order of 10 – 20 m/s can be measured at the gap of the spark plug in modern DISI engines. The resolved velocity profile in the calculated case is dependent on the mesh resolution. Figure 6.13 presents the velocity profile obtained for the different meshes. Some differences between the profiles can be noticed. The velocity profile at the fine mesh and the medium mesh is generally similar with more smooth transitions at the fine mesh. The velocity profile at the coarse mesh differs more. The range of the generated high velocity after the gap is shorter and visibly higher velocities are obtained at the wall of the center electrode and at the edges of the ground electrode. The recirculation zones after the electrodes are visibly smaller and of higher velocity magnitude. The differences in the velocity profiles between the investigated mesh resolutions directly affect the shape of the spark channel which movement in the model is based on the velocity interpolated from the cell-centered value for each particle representing the spark.

Figure 6.12: Three different meshes used to investigate the mesh influence on the results — fine (left), medium (middle), coarse (right).

Figure 6.13: Velocity field resolved on the fine mesh (left), medium mesh (middle) and coarse mesh (right).

Figure 6.14 shows the deflected spark channel at the calculated ignition timing with the precursor plotted at every particle of the spark showing the calculated position of the ignition. Small differences in the calculated shape of the spark channel influence the local curvature of the spark modifying the heat transfer from the spark, the calculated temperature and the calculated precursor. The precursor and the local curvature, corresponding to the curvature κ_2 in the model, are plotted for investigated cases on separate graphs in

Fig. 6.15. The normalized position along the spark channel starts at the center electrode and ends at the ground electrode. The spark bending from around 0.2 to around 0.8 of its length is visible as an increased curvature in this region. The curvature result also shows the differences in the shape of the spark channels. There are two visible maxima of the curvature for the coarse mesh which correspond to the maxima of the precursor at around 0.4 and 0.6 of the spark length. For the medium and fine meshes, the curvature profiles are similar with only one maximum at around 0.4 of the spark length corresponding to the maximum of the precursor at the same location. As for the calculated ignition delay it was 0.118 ms for the fine mesh, 0.120 ms for the medium mesh and 0.121 ms for the coarse mesh. These small differences can be related to the local curvature of the spark at the calculated ignition point.

Figure 6.14: Deflected spark channel at the calculated ignition time with the precursor plotted at the spark particles for the fine mesh (left), medium mesh (middle), coarse mesh (right).

Figure 6.15: Absolute value of curvature κ_2 (left) and the precursor (right) along the spark channel for different meshes.

Considering minor differences between the results obtained for the medium and for the fine mesh and more distinguishable differences in the results of the curvature and the precursor obtained for the coarse mesh, the medium mesh refined up to the element size of 0.1 mm at the spark gap will be used in the real engine cases in the following chapters.

Additionally, the mesh refined to the element size of 0.1 mm at the ignition point would safely allow to resolve the surface of the initial flame kernel of the diameter of 0.5 mm.

6.9 Influence of the spark resolution on the ignition position and delay time

In this section the influence of the number of particles representing the spark channel on the position of the ignition and the ignition delay time is investigated. The setup is similar as in the previous section, where the influence of the mesh resolution was investigated. The medium mesh refined up to the element size of 0.1 mm at the spark gap is used. Five cases are calculated with 50, 100, 200, 400 and 800 particles representing the spark channel in the ignition model. Figure 6.16 presents the spark channel at the ignition timing with the plotted precursor for 50, 200 and 800 particles.

Figure 6.16: Deflected spark channel at the calculated ignition time with the precursor plotted at the spark for 50 particles (left), 200 particles (middle), 800 particles (right).

Figure 6.17: Curvature (left) and precursor (right) along the spark channel for the different number of particles representing the spark.

There are no visible differences in the shape of the spark, which is confirmed by the local curvature along the spark channel plotted in Fig. 6.17. A noticeable difference in the

local curvature is at around 0.1 of the normalized length, which is due to the interaction with the wall of the center electrode and does not influence the precursor. The other difference in the local curvature is at around 0.6 of the normalized length. This difference corresponds to the difference in the precursor between 0.5 and 0.6 of the normalized length. The higher the curvature in this region, the larger is the precursor with only a small difference in the overall profile between 200, 400 and 800 particles as shown in Fig. 6.17. Despite these differences, the highest curvature is the same in all cases and at the 0.4 of the normalized length. The precursor along the spark channel shows that in every case the ignition point is calculated at the location of the highest curvature. Based on the results presented in this section the discretization of the spark channel with 200 particles at the gap of 1.0 mm is sufficient, while 100 or 50 particles might affect the result of the precursor. In the engine cases in the following chapters, the spark channel will be discretized with 200 particles.

Chapter 7

Numerical and experimental investigations

This chapter presents a number of cases calculated with the proposed ignition model to verify its performance and consistence of the provided results with experimental data. The new model is implemented into the AVL FireTM solver and all simulations presented in this work are performed with use of this solver. In section 7.1 the spark discharge process in high velocity flow field is modeled. The results of the spark channel deflection as well as the current and voltage in the secondary electrical circuit are compared to the experimental data of Kufferath et al. [78]. In section 7.2 the proposed model is used to predict the onset of ignition in the 3D CFD simulation of the AVL Single Cylinder Research Engine. In section 7.3 the ignition model is used for 3D CFD combustion simulation in the barrel-type Opposed-Piston (OP) engine developed at Warsaw University of Technology.

7.1 Spark discharge process in high velocity flow field

The first CFD simulations with the new ignition model concern the spark discharge process in a high velocity flow field. The goal is to reproduce experiments performed by Kufferath et al. [78] and to compare the results with the measured data. The experimental setup from [78] is given in Fig. 7.1. The test stand consists of an ignition system, a spark plug placed in a pressure vessel, a nozzle, a compressed air supply, a high-speed camera for spark visualization and a rotameter to measure the massflow. The nozzle is placed next to the spark plug in the pressure vessel and generates the velocity which deflects the spark

channel during the discharge. The velocity is calculated from the nozzle diameter and the massflow measured with the rotameter. The massflow is adjusted with the pressure regulator at the outlet of the pressure vessel. The current and the voltage in the secondary circuit of the ignition system are measured during the discharge event with an oscilloscope. Table 7.1 summarizes the properties of the secondary electrical circuit and experimental conditions. The measurements are performed for three different velocity levels at the spark plug — 8 m/s, 12 m/s and 16 m/s.

Table 7.1: Experimental setup for the spark discharge measurement.

Parameter	Value
Initial energy	140 mJ
Resistance	10 k Ω
Inductance	40 H
Electrode gap	0.65 mm
Chamber temperature	293 K
Chamber pressure	5 bar
Velocity at the spark plug	8 m/s, 12 m/s, 16 m/s

Figure 7.1: Experimental setup from [78].

The numerical setup is presented in Fig. 7.2. The computational domain includes a small cubical volume around the spark plug electrodes with the mesh size refined to 0.1 mm. A velocity inlet boundary condition is applied at the inlet wall and the pressure outlet boundary condition is applied at the opposite wall. The remaining walls are treated as symmetry. Each case is firstly calculated as a steady state to obtain the velocity field within the domain. Then the time-dependent simulation of the spark discharge is performed. The spark is represented with 400 particles initialized between the spark electrodes at the instance of the breakdown. The reason of using 400 particles instead of 200 determined in Chapter 6 is motivated by the significant deflection of the spark in the

experiment. The dynamics of the spark channel and electrical circuit are calculated with the proposed model. The given velocity field deflects the spark plasma during the discharge. If the spark is long enough, a restrike happens and a new spark is formed between the electrodes as long as there is energy available in the electrical circuit. The three cases corresponding to the experiment are calculated.

Figure 7.2: Numerical setup (left) and numerical mesh (right).

Figures 7.3, 7.4, 7.5 present a comparison between the calculated and the measured current, voltage and power in the secondary electrical circuit during the spark discharge process. The inter-electrode voltage is calculated with Eq. (6.2.3) and the current is calculated with Eq. (6.2.2). Both measurements and simulations predict multiple restrikes in the considered cases. Furthermore, the higher the velocity, the more restrikes happen during the single discharge event. Overall, a good agreement between the model and the experiment is obtained in the current level and the duration of the discharge process. As for the voltage and power, the calculation matches the measurement only during the first breakdown. During the next breakdowns difference between calculated and measured voltage comes from the fact that in the experiment the spark deposited after the restrike is already elongated and deflected, while the model does not include the stochastic character of restrikes and initializes the new spark channel directly between the electrodes after the restrike. Because the energy available in the electrical circuit decreases with time, the power supplied by the electrical circuit also decreases during the consecutive breakdowns. As a result, the ignition is expected to take place during the first breakdown, where the model shows a very good agreement with the experiment. In the following breakdowns the ignition is less probable due to the decreased power supply. The power graphs in Figs. 7.3, 7.4, 7.5 also include an average heat transfer calculated as a total energy divided by the length of the discharge. Results show that the instantaneous heat transfer to the spark channel can differ significantly from the average over the whole discharge

process. The assumption about the average heat source is made in such ignition models as SparkCIMM [9] or CADIM [8, 57]. The presented results clearly show that in case of high velocity flow field close to the spark plug this assumption is incorrect and may cause an error in prediction of the ignition delay. In all three calculated cases the instantaneous

Figure 7.3: Comparison between the proposed model and the experiment [78] for 8 m/s. The current and voltage (left) and the supplied power (right).

Figure 7.4: Comparison between the proposed model and the experiment [78] for 12 m/s. The current and voltage (left) and the supplied power (right).

Figure 7.5: Comparison between the proposed model and the experiment [78] for 16 m/s. The current and voltage (left) and the supplied power (right).

power level increases during the single breakdown, as the voltage increases with lengthening of the spark channel. The new model proposed in this work is capable of the correct calculation of the increasing power supplied by the ignition system, which during the first breakdown becomes significantly higher than the average power supplied during the whole discharge process. This allows for the correct calculation of the temperature at the surface of the spark channel and ignition delay of the mixture.

Figures 7.6, 7.7, 7.8 show the spark plasma channel captured with a high-speed camera and compare it to the result obtained with the proposed model during the first breakdown event. The spark channel clearly deflects under the strong flow generated by the nozzle. The duration of the first breakdown varies with the velocity. The higher the velocity, the

Figure 7.6: Comparison of the spark deflection for 8 m/s during the first breakdown between the proposed model (top) and the experiment [78] (bottom).

Figure 7.7: Comparison of the spark deflection for 12 m/s during the first breakdown between the proposed model (top) and the experiment [78] (bottom).

Figure 7.8: Comparison of the spark deflection for 16 m/s during the first breakdown between the proposed model (top) and the experiment [78] (bottom).

faster is the deflection of the spark and the voltage rise which depends on the length of the spark channel (from Eq. 6.2.5). When the inter-electrode voltage reaches the breakdown voltage, a restrike happens. The presented results show that the shape and length of the

evolving curve is well represented by the moving particles for all three cases. Also the duration of the first breakdown event is correctly predicted and lasts around 0.4 ms for 8 m/s case, around 0.3 ms for 12 m/s and around 0.2 ms for 16 m/s case.

The experimental and numerical results presented in this section show that the velocity field in the vicinity of the spark plug has a strong influence on the dynamics of the plasma channel during the spark discharge. An increased velocity may lead to faster deflection of the spark and shorter duration of the single breakdown. For very high velocities it may be possible that the breakdown duration is shorter than the delay time required for ignition of the mixture which may cause a misfire. The numerical results show a good agreement with the measurement during the first breakdown. This confirms that the model correctly predicts the spark discharge process and can be used in engine cases, where the ignition is also expected to take place during the first breakdown of the spark.

7.2 Spark Ignition and combustion in the AVL Research Engine

This subsection presents experimental and numerical results of the AVL FM540 single cylinder research engine. Firstly, the AVL FM540 engine is described. Then, the load points measured at the test stand are defined and the approach to numerical simulations of the engine operation is described. To assess the performance of the proposed ignition model under real engine operation conditions, the experimental measurements of the AVL engine are compared to the results of numerical simulations and conclusions are drawn.

7.2.1 AVL FM540 Research Engine

The AVL FM540 (Fig. 7.9) is a single cylinder DISI research engine. It is equipped with a wall guided direct injection system and the injection nozzle is mounted below the intake valves. To achieve a homogeneous mixture, the injection takes place during the intake stroke. This engine is specially designed for Controlled-Auto-Ignition (CAI) combustion cycles under part load conditions, using high EGR rates to provide the necessary conditions for auto-ignition operation. Therefore, the engine is equipped with an internal exhaust gas recirculation system consisting of an electro-hydraulic actuator, which is able to open one exhaust valve during the intake stroke (the so called re-breathing). Further-

more, the valve train is equipped with intake and exhaust camphasers to optimize the cylinder charging at different engine speeds. The adjustable valve train also allows for a conventional SI engine operation. The general engine information is given in Table 7.2.

Table 7.2: AVL FM540 research engine information.

Engine type	1-cylinder 4V DOHC
Displacement	500 cm ³
Bore/Stroke	86/86 mm
Compression ratio	11.5 (up to 14 possible)
Injection	Direct-Injection
Rotational speed	1000 – 6000 rpm
Spark plug gap	0.8 mm

Figure 7.9: AVL FM540 research engine on the test stand.

7.2.2 Investigated operation points

To investigate the performance of the proposed ignition model, four engine load points experimentally measured at the test stand are chosen to be calculated with the new ignition model that is implemented into the AVL FireTM solver. The operation points concern the engine running on partial loads. In order to diversify measurement data and conditions for model validation, each measurement is done for different engine rotational speeds. The summary of considered load points is given in Table 7.3. One of the results

that is compared between the measurement and calculation is the pressure profile over a single engine cycle. Due to cycle-to-cycle variations in the engine operation, choosing only a single cycle as a representative measurement data is incorrect. A common practice is to collect data from several engine cycles (in this work it is 100 cycles) and perform an averaging. The pressure profile averaged over 100 cycles can be compared to the pressure result from CFD RANS simulations. The measured and averaged pressure profiles from 100 cycles are presented in Fig. 7.10 for each considered operation point.

Table 7.3: Summary of the investigated load points of the AVL FM540 research engine.

Operation Point	OP2252	OP2359	OP2504	OP2640
RPM	1250	1500	2000	3000
Equivalence ratio	0.849	0.844	0.880	0.889
Mean EGR	16.1%	13.2%	16.9%	18.9%
Spark timing (degCA aTDC)	-17	-17	-22	-28
IMEP (bar)	2.73	3.4	2.86	2.5

Figure 7.10: Measured and averaged pressure profiles of the chosen operation points of the AVL FM540 engine.

7.2.3 Numerical approach

The numerical RANS simulations are performed with use of the AVL FireTM code with the new ignition model implemented and include four cycles — exhaust, intake, compression and expansion. During the exhaust and intake strokes full engine geometry with intake/exhaust ports and valves is considered (Fig. 7.11a) to model the scavenging process. During the compression and expansion strokes, when intake/exhaust ports are physically closed, only the geometry of the combustion chamber is considered (Fig. 7.11b). Numerical mesh in AVL FireTM can comprise of tetrahedron, hexahedron or polyhedron elements. The preferable element shape for engine simulations is polyhedron, which allows for mesh refinement at sharp edges, preserving details of the model. It also allows for smooth transition from the refined details to the regular mesh size. The numerical mesh for these simulations (Fig. 7.12) is prepared with the AVL Fame Engine Plus Poly tool which automatically generates moving meshes for engine simulations. The maximum size of element is 1.0 mm refined at sharp edges to preserve geometry details. The mesh size in the vicinity of the spark plug, where the ignition takes place is refined to 0.1 mm to correctly represent the spark plug geometry and initialize the combustion process. The full mesh with intake/exhaust ports and valves at BDC consists of $\sim 2\,200\,000$ elements, while the combustion chamber mesh at TDC with refined ignition area consists of $\sim 360\,000$ elements.

Figure 7.11: Geometry of the computational domain at TDC; a) the full model with opened valves, b) the combustion chamber with closed valves.

The turbulence in simulations is modeled with the k - ζ - f turbulence model [79]. The fuel spray is modeled with around 20000 stochastic Lagrangian spray parcels coupled to the gas phase via source terms. The simulation time-step during the ignition and combustion is set to 0.1 degCA(1250 rpm), 0.1 degCA(1500 rpm), 0.125 degCA(2000 rpm), 0.2 degCA(3000 rpm). In order to show the effect of the proposed ignition model on the

Figure 7.12: Numerical mesh of the combustion chamber (left) refined around the spark plug (right).

results, two cases are calculated for every considered operation point. The first case is calculated without any ignition model. The flame kernel of the diameter of 0.5 mm [44] is simply initialized directly between the spark electrodes at the ignition timing. The following flame propagation is handled by the G -equation combustion model solved with the level-set approach. The second case is calculated with the proposed ignition model — at the instance of the spark breakdown, a spark channel consisting of 200 Lagrangian particles is initialized between the spark electrodes. The model calculates the deflection of the spark, the ignition delay and the final location of the ignition point along the spark channel. When the ignition criterion is reached, the flame kernel is initialized at the calculated ignition point similarly as in the first case. Then, the flame propagation is also handled by the G -equation combustion model.

7.2.4 Results and discussion

This section presents results of the numerical simulations of the AVL FM540 engine and compares them to the measured data. Since this work is focused on the ignition and combustion modeling, results of the scavenging, fuel injection, evaporation and mixture formation processes are not presented here. Only the resulting velocity field and mixture composition at the plane cut through the cylinder at the ignition timing are presented. After the discussion on the conditions in the combustion chamber at the ignition timing and close to the spark plug, the results of the spark discharge and ignition are presented. Finally, global results of the pressure profile and the rate of heat release (ROHR) are presented to discuss the influence of the ignition process on the combustion simulations.

Equivalence ratio

Figure 7.13 shows the equivalence ratio at the plane cut through the cylinder with an enhanced area around the spark plug for all four investigated cases. From Table 7.2 in every investigated case the engine runs on a similar global equivalence ratio ($\phi = 0.85 - 0.89$). From Fig. 7.13 it can be concluded that differences in engine load and speed result in a different fuel distribution in the combustion chamber. Although the global stoichiometry remains at the same level, local regions of lean and rich mixture occur in different places. For the operation point OP2252 a rich mixture with $\phi > 1.0$ is present close to the exhaust

Figure 7.13: Results of equivalence ratio at the onset of ignition.

ports and the spark plug, while a region of lean mixture with $\phi < 1.0$ can be noticed between the intake ports and the piston bowl. For the operation point OP2359 a region of rich mixture is similar as for OP2252 with an additional pocket close to the injector. The operation point OP2504 is different than the two previous cases. Almost stoichiometric mixture ($\phi \approx 1.0$) is present below the intake ports and close to the spark plug, while a lean mixture of $\phi < 0.8$ is close to the exhaust ports. Yet another fuel distribution appears in the operation point OP2640. Here only two pockets of stoichiometric mixture appear on the right of the spark plug and on the left of the exhaust ports. The remaining area is of a slightly lean ($\phi \approx 0.9$) and lean ($\phi < 0.8$) mixture close to the injector. The described

results concern only the plane cut through the cylinder and a different distribution can happen in the rest of the cylinder volume. However, the spark plug is visible at the plane cut and the equivalence ratio at the spark plug is of importance for the ignition process. In Fig. 7.13 also the area around the spark plug is enhanced. For the operation point OP2252 the mixture at the spark plug is $\phi \approx 1.05$, for the operation point OP2359 $\phi \approx 1.17$, for the operation point OP2504 $\phi \approx 0.93$ and for the operation point OP2640 $\phi \approx 0.88$. These differences can have an effect on the ignition delay time calculated with the new ignition model (see Fig. 6.9).

Velocity field

The other parameter which is expected to have influence on the ignition is the velocity field around the spark plug. A high velocity can significantly deflect the spark channel during the discharge and drag away the ignition point from the spark electrodes. Figure 7.14 presents velocity vectors at the plane cut through the cylinder with an enhanced area around the spark plug. The direction of the charge motion is similar in all four operation points. At the spark plug the flow directs towards the intake ports but the magnitude of the velocity differs visibly between cases. For the operation points OP2252 and OP2359

Figure 7.14: Results of velocity vectors at the onset of ignition.

the velocity at the spark electrodes reaches only 1.5 m/s and a rather small deflection of the spark channel is expected. For the operation point OP2504 the velocity at the spark gap reaches 4.0 m/s and for the operation point OP2640 7.0 m/s. For these two cases a more distinct deflection of the spark channel is expected.

Spark discharge and ignition

The 3D results of the spark discharge and the resulting ignition location are given in Figs. 7.15–7.18. During the simulations the spark is initialized at the instance of the breakdown with 200 particles evenly distributed between the electrodes. The proposed ignition model calculates the deflection of the spark, the temperature at the spark surface and the precursor of the ignition at the same time for every particle representing the spark channel. At the end of the ignition calculation, the flame kernel is initialized at the calculated position. In all four calculated operation points, the spark becomes deflected towards the intake ports. As expected, based on the velocity results, the spark is only slightly deflected for cases OP2252 and OP2359, where velocities are low. The more distinct deflection of the spark is noticeable for the operation point OP2504 and the most considerable deflection appears for the operation point OP2640, where the velocity close to the spark plug is the highest. In all cases the model predicts the ignition to take place at the most curved region of the spark channel. It is caused by the concave curvature of the spark surface, which has a negative sign and decreases the positive curvature of the cylindrical surface effectively reducing the overall curvature at the spark surface. With the reduced curvature, heat transfer is decreased, resulting in the increased temperature at the surface and the shorter ignition delay.

The calculated delay of the ignition in every case is given in Table 7.4. The delay in milliseconds is of similar order for every case (0.115 – 0.171). For cases OP2252 and OP2359, where the spark has similar shape and the effect of the curvature on the ignition delay should be similar, a slightly longer delay is calculated for the case OP2359, which most probably results from the higher equivalence ratio at the spark plug. In Fig. 7.17 it can be noticed that for the case OP2504, the deflection of the spark at the ignition location is the sharpest among all cases and the curvature effect on the ignition delay should be the strongest. Indeed, the shortest ignition delay is predicted for this case. In operation point OP2640, the spark becomes deflected very fast because of the high velocity and at the time of ignition the spark is noticeably longer and smoother than in

Figure 7.15: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP2252.

Figure 7.16: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP2359.

Figure 7.17: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP2504.

Figure 7.18: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP2640.

the operation point OP2504. The curvature effect in this case is smaller and the ignition delay is longer than in OP2504 case, although the equivalence ratio is slightly lower at the spark location. When comparing the ignition delay in degCA, one can notice that the longest delay is for the operation point OP2640, at which the engine has the highest rotational speed (3000 rpm). The effect of the ignition delay will be the most noticeable

at the pressure vs. degCA results for the higher rotational speeds where a similar delay in milliseconds translates to a longer delay in degCA. Generally it can be stated that the results of the spark discharge and ignition are in agreement with the description of the model (effect of the velocity field on the shape of the spark, effect of the equivalence ratio and the curvature on the ignition delay).

Table 7.4: Summary of the ignition delays calculated for the AVL FM540 engine.

Operation Point	OP2252	OP2359	OP2504	OP2640
Ignition delay (ms)	0.170	0.181	0.115	0.131
Ignition delay (degCA)	1.28	1.63	1.39	2.35

Effect of the ignition model on the combustion process

To show the influence of the ignition model on the overall combustion process in the engine additional cases with a simple spherical ignition model have been calculated for every operation point. In the spherical ignition model, the flame kernel is initialized directly between the spark electrodes at the spark timing. It means that the spark channel is not considered at all and comparing to the new ignition model proposed in this work, the ignition delay and the position of the flame kernel are not calculated. This actually leads to an earlier flame initiation and start of the flame propagation. The comparison of the ignition process for the simple spherical model and the new spark ignition model is presented in Figs. 7.19–7.22, where each figure corresponds to one of the operation points. For every operation point two instants of time are shown — the moment of the ignition timing and the moment of the flame kernel initiation in the new ignition model. The difference of the ignition stage is clearly visible and similar in all cases. At the ignition timing the spark channel is initialized in the new ignition model, while in the simple ignition model the flame kernel is initialized at the same instant. During the ignition delay calculated with the new model, the flame kernel already grows in calculations with the simple model. Finally, when the kernel is initialized in the new model, the flame is already grown in the simple model and the combustion is at a later stage. The difference in the progress of the combustion process generated during the ignition phase cannot be compensated after the ignition is finished and has an effect on the final results of engine simulations, such as the pressure profile and the ROHR.

Figure 7.23 presents the pressure profile and the ROHR calculated with the new ignition model and with the spherical ignition model as well as the measurement data from

Figure 7.19: Ignition process with the proposed model (top) and with the simple model (bottom) for OP2252.

Figure 7.20: Ignition process with the proposed model (top) and with the simple model (bottom) for OP2359.

Figure 7.21: Ignition process with the proposed model (top) and with the simple model (bottom) for OP2504.

Figure 7.22: Ignition process with the proposed model (top) and with the simple model (bottom) for OP2640.

the test stand. It can be noticed that the results obtained with the newly proposed model generally match the measurement very well in all investigated cases. The start of the pressure rise at the beginning of combustion is well represented thanks to the ignition delay calculated with the ignition model. The following rate of the pressure rise, which directly corresponds to the ROHR also matches the measurement very well which confirms the performance of the G -equation combustion model. The calculated pressure profile agrees with the measurement up to the point where the peak pressure is reached. After that, combustion comes to an end and the remaining flame is slowed down and quenched as

Figure 7.23: Measured and calculated pressure and ROHR profiles for the considered operation points of the AVL FM540 engine.

it approaches the walls of the combustion chamber. At the time when simulations were done for the AVL FM540 engine, the G -equation model in AVL FireTM did not include a detailed description of the flame quenching close to the walls, which resulted in a slightly overestimated pressure during the expansion stroke. As for the simulations with the simple spherical ignition model the lack of the ignition delay calculation results in the earlier start of combustion and rise of the pressure. In the effect also the higher peak pressure is predicted which can have a significant influence in case of knock modeling. Table 7.5 presents the Crank Angle of 50% heat released (CA50) for all investigated cases including measurement data, simulations with the new ignition model and simulations with the simple spherical ignition model. It can be noticed that the engine was running with CA50 between 4.90 and 5.00 degCA aTDC and the CA50 from calculations with the new ignition model matches the measurement CA50 with a small error in all cases. On the other hand, the calculations with the simple ignition model predict an earlier CA50 which corresponds to already described results of the pressure profile. The differences in CA50 between the cases calculated with the new and the simple ignition model are given at the

end of Table 7.5. These differences originate from the ignition delay given in Table 7.4. It confirms that the lack of prediction of the ignition delay in the simple model at the ignition stage is not compensated during the combustion which translates to the differences in CA50 between the models. The longest ignition delay (in degCA) and the biggest difference in CA50 is obtained for the case OP2640 (3000 rpm), while the shortest ignition delay (in degCA) and the smallest difference in CA50 for the case OP2252 (1250 rpm). However, the differences of CA50 given in Table 7.5 slightly differ from the ignition delay times predicted by the new ignition model for individual cases. Although these differences are small, they can come from the initial stage of flame propagation influenced by the position at which the flame kernel is introduced.

Table 7.5: Comparison of the CA50 timing for the new ignition model, simple ignition model and the measurement.

Operation Point	OP2252	OP2359	OP2504	OP2640
Measurement CA50 (degCA)	5.67	6.00	5.57	4.90
New model CA50 (degCA)	5.50	5.61	5.76	5.03
Simple model CA50 (degCA)	4.46	4.08	3.59	2.21
Difference between models (degCA)	1.04	1.53	2.18	2.83

The last result presented in this section in Fig. 7.24 shows the propagation of the G -surface representing the turbulent flame front for the case OP2640. This result is only to visualize the combustion process in the calculated cases and does not directly relate to the ignition process. However, the effect of the ignition modeling can be noticed as a small shift of the flame kernel in the direction of the ground electrode at the early stage of combustion. The flame propagation has similar character in the rest of the investigated cases.

Figure 7.24: Propagation of the G -surface representing the turbulent flame front.

7.3 Spark Ignition and combustion in the Barrel-Type Opposed-Piston Engine

This section describes the application of the proposed ignition model in numerical modeling of the combustion process in the PAMAR-4 research engine. Similarly as in the previous subsection, the PAMAR-4 engine is briefly described and the approach to numerical simulations is presented. The experimental measurements from the test stand are used to evaluate the performance of the new ignition model implemented into the AVL FireTM software.

7.3.1 PAMAR-4 Research Engine

The PAMAR-4 engine is a 2-cylinder, 2-stroke Opposed-Piston (OP) barrel engine (Figs. 7.25). It has been developed at Warsaw University of Technology under the Polish-Norwegian Cooperation Research conducted by the National Research and Development Center. An OP engine is a subtype of internal combustion engine with two pistons reciprocating opposite to each other, both working in one cylinder. As a result there is no cylinder head in this configuration and the combustion chamber of a cylindrical shape is formed between the two pistons. The OP engines can work as a 4-stroke, but most of them are 2-stroke engines and scavenging is usually controlled by piston-ported valves. A comprehensive review of different types of OP engines is given in [80]. The PAMAR-4 engine is using a wobble plate mechanism to transfer the power from two cylinders and four pistons to the single shaft. With this design several cylinders can be arranged around a single shaft with cylinders' axes parallel to the shaft axis resulting in the characteristic barrel shape of the engine. The PAMAR-4 engine is designed to work with different fuels (gaseous or liquid) and with different combustion modes (Spark-Ignition, Compression-Ignition or Homogeneous-Charge-Compression-Ignition) using Variable Compression Ratio (VCR), Variable Port Timing (VPT) and Variable Phase Shift (VPS) between the pistons. In this work only conventional SI operation with DI fuel injection is considered. The fuel is injected perpendicular to the axis of the cylinder with a hollow-cone injector through one of the seven ports placed around the combustion chamber (Fig. 7.27). The ignition is realized with two conventional spark plugs also placed in the ports around the combustion chamber. The general information on the PAMAR-4 engine is given in Table 7.6.

Table 7.6: PAMAR-4 research engine information.

Engine type	2-stroke, Opposed-Piston
Number of cylinders/pistons	2/4
Displacement	$\sim 1800 \text{ cm}^3$
Bore/Stroke	55/190($\times 2$) mm
Compression ratio	8.5 (up to 18 possible with VCR)
Rotational speed	400 – 1500 rpm
Injection	Direct-Injection
Turbocharging	Two-Stage up to 4 bar
Spark plug gap	1 mm

Figure 7.25: PAMAR-4 research engine.

7.3.2 Investigated operation points

Two operation points of the PAMAR-4 engine experimentally investigated at the test stand are chosen to be analyzed and calculated with the new ignition model proposed in this work. Operation points OP1970 and OP2245 are summarized in Table 7.7. The operation points represent similar engine load and rotational speed but differ in the injection strategy and ignition. In case of the operation point OP1970 the fuel injection is split into two portions and injected with a single injector placed in the port P5, while in the operation point OP2245, there are two injectors placed in ports P2/P6 and fuel injection is also split for each injector. In the operation point OP2245 the fuel is injected later during the compression stroke ($-90/-55 \text{ degCA}$) than in OP1970 ($-50/-30 \text{ degCA}$). As for the spark plugs, in case of the operation point OP1970 the spark plugs are placed in ports P2/P4, 90 degrees next to each other, while in the operation point OP2245 the spark plugs are placed in ports P3/P7, opposite to each other. Due to cycle-to-cycle vari-

ations in the engine operation, data from 100 cycles are collected and averaged (Fig. 7.26) to be used for comparison with the results of CFD RANS numerical simulations.

Table 7.7: Summary of the investigated operation points of the PAMAR-4 engine.

Operation Point	OP1970	OP2245
RPM	500	425
Equivalence ratio	0.565	0.595
Boost pressure (bar(a))	1.09	1.11
Mean EGR	0.5%	0.0%
Injector position (Fig. 7.27)	P5	P2/P6
Injection timing (degCA aTDC)	-90/-55	-50/-30
Spark position (Fig. 7.27)	P2/P4	P3/P7
Spark timing (degCA aTDC)	-11	-4
IMEP (bar)	6.4	6.6

Figure 7.26: Measured and averaged pressure profiles of the chosen operation points of the PAMAR-4 engine.

7.3.3 Numerical approach

Similarly as for the AVL FM540 engine, numerical RANS simulations with the new ignition model are performed for the PAMAR-4 engine. Since PAMAR-4 is a 2-stroke engine, simulations cover the scavenging, compression and expansion processes. Only one of the two cylinders is modeled. During the scavenging both intake and exhaust ports are opened and burnt gases are replaced with fresh air. It requires modeling of the full geometry, including the combustion chamber, intake/exhaust ports and a part of the intake and exhaust manifolds as presented in Fig. 7.27a. When intake and exhaust ports are physically closed, only the geometry of the combustion chamber is considered. Figure 7.27b presents the shape of the combustion chamber with seven ports which hold spark plugs,

injectors and pressure sensors. Boundary conditions come from the measurements done at the test stand for the corresponding operation points (intake/exhaust pressure fluctuations measured with a fast pressure sensors in intake/exhaust manifolds, cylinder wall temperatures measured with thermocouples). The full mesh used to calculate the scaveng-

Figure 7.27: Geometry of the computational domain; a) during the scavenging process, b) during the combustion process.

Figure 7.28: Numerical mesh of the combustion chamber; a) for the operation point OP1970, b) for the operation point OP2245.

ing process consists of $\sim 1\,500\,000$ elements at BDC, while the combustion chamber mesh at TDC with refined ignition area consists of $\sim 290\,000$ elements. The cross-section of the numerical mesh through the combustion chamber is given in Fig. 7.28 and shows different positioning of the spark plugs for OP1970 and OP2245 operation points. The injection is modeled in the same manner as for the AVL FM540 engine, with Lagrangian particles. The time step during the ignition and combustion is set to 0.05 degCA (500 rpm). Since results of the AVL FM540 engine showed that the ignition delay calculated with the proposed ignition model has small influence on the overall pressure profile for cases

with low rotational speed, the PAMAR-4 cases are calculated only with the new ignition model and no comparison to the simple ignition model is done. At the ignition timing two independent spark channels, each represented by 200 particles, are initialized between the electrodes of the corresponding spark plugs. The ignition model calculates the delay time and the position of two individual ignition points. Due to possibly different conditions at the locations of the spark plugs, the calculated ignition delay may slightly differ between them. The use of the G -equation combustion model solved with the level-set approach allows to track the propagation of the flame initialized at two distinct points independently, as in the simulations of the PAMAR-4 engine. At some point during the combustion two flame fronts merge and form a single flame surface, which propagates until the end of the combustion process.

7.3.4 Results and discussion

This section presents results of numerical simulations of the PAMAR-4 engine and compares them to the measured data. Again, the attention is paid to the modeling of the ignition and combustion processes and results of the scavenging, fuel injection, evaporation and mixture formation are not presented and discussed here. Only the resulting velocity field and mixture composition at the plane cut through the combustion chamber at the ignition timing are presented for both cases. To discuss the influence of the ignition process on the overall combustion simulation in the PAMAR-4 engine, the results of the spark discharge, ignition as well as pressure and ROHR profiles are presented.

Equivalence ratio

Figure 7.29 presents the equivalence ratio at the plane cut through the combustion chamber for both investigated cases. The areas close to the spark plugs are enhanced. The distribution of the fuel in the combustion chamber at ignition timing results from the fuel injection, evaporation and interaction with the charge motion in the cylinder during the compression stroke. For the operation point OP1970 it is strongly non-uniform with very lean area ($\phi < 0.4$) close to the ports P3 and P4. However, some of the fuel reached the crevice of the port P4 during the mixture formation and a rich mixture is present at the gap of the spark plug placed in the port P4. This should allow for a firm ignition at this location, but the following flame propagation from the P4 location is uncertain

due to a very lean mixture surrounding it. The equivalence ratio at the gap of the spark plug at the port P2 is around $\phi = 0.4$. A region of rich mixture can be noticed between the ports P1 and P2 and the flame should propagate from the ignition point at the port P2 throughout the combustion chamber. In case of the operation point OP2245, the fuel injection from two injectors placed opposite to each other and performed later during the compression stroke resulted in much more uniform fuel distribution than in the operation point OP1970. Generally, the mixture is leaner in the middle of the combustion chamber and some rich regions can be noticed in the vicinity of the ports P4 and P6. At the ports P3 and P7, where the spark plugs are placed, the mixture is also leaner than the average equivalence ratio, varying from $\phi = 0.3$ to $\phi = 0.6$. At the both spark plugs conditions for ignition are similar, which should result in a similar ignition delay calculated with the new ignition model.

Figure 7.29: Results of equivalence ratio at the onset of ignition.

Velocity field

The velocity vectors presented in Fig. 7.30 clearly show a uniform swirl motion of the mixture around the axis of the cylinder. The swirl motion is formed during the scavenging process and is a result of the design of the intake ports. Although the velocities in the combustion chamber reach 4 m/s in the investigated cases, the spark plugs placed in the

ports are hidden from the main swirl motion resulting in very low velocities at the spark plug gaps (lower than 1 m/s). Therefore, only a small deflection of the spark channel is expected during the ignition process. The highest velocity is at the gap of the spark plug in the port P3 of the operation point OP2245 (1.5 m/s). The spark plasma channel deposited at this location can become slightly deflected before reaching the ignition criterion.

Figure 7.30: Results of velocity vectors at the onset of ignition.

Spark discharge and ignition

The 3D results of the spark discharge and the resulting ignition locations are presented in Figs. 7.31 and 7.32. The results show the spark channel initialized at the spark ignition timing, the flame kernel initialized after the calculated ignition delay and at the calculated position along the spark channel and the growing flame at around 0.2 ms after the ignition. It can be noticed that the deflection of each investigated spark is minor, which is in agreement with the velocity results discussed in the previous paragraph. The most significant deflection of the spark channel appears at the spark plug P3 of the operation point OP2245, where also the velocity is the highest. However, this deflection is still rather small and the ignition kernel is only slightly shifted from the center point between the spark electrodes. Table 7.8 presents the ignition delay calculated for the considered ignition points. The delay in ms is similar for the sparks at the locations P4 of the op-

Figure 7.31: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP1970.

Figure 7.32: Spark discharge and ignition for the operation point OP2245.

eration point OP1970 and at the locations P3 and P7 of the operation point OP2245. A longer delay is calculated for the spark at the location P2 of the operation point OP1970. The reach mixture at the gap of this spark plug has a higher density and a higher heat capacity, which require more energy (more time) to reach the ignition criterion. Table 7.8 also presents the ignition delay in degCA. Due to a low rotational speed of the investigated operation points of the PAMAR-4 engine, the ignition delay calculated with the new ignition model is only 0.44 – 0.69 degCA. The error in the CA50 result made without considering the ignition delay would be accordingly small. This result is in agreement with

the observations made for the AVL engine cases — the ignition delay calculated with the ignition model is more meaningful for high rotational speed engine cases, while for low rotational speed engine cases it has small effect on the overall result.

Table 7.8: Summary of the ignition delays calculated for the PAMAR-4 engine.

Case	OP1970(P2)	OP1970(P4)	OP2245(P3)	OP2245(P7)
Ignition delay (ms)	0.177	0.229	0.177	0.174
Ignition delay (degCA)	0.53	0.69	0.45	0.44

In addition to the result of the location of the ignition point, the results of the growing kernel at around 0.2 ms after the ignition are shown. It is interesting to compare the size of the kernel between the considered cases at the same time after the ignition. The kernels at the location P4 of the operation point OP1970 and at the locations P3 and P7 of the operation point OP2245 have grown to the similar size, because the conditions for their growth are similar (similar equivalence ratio). The rich mixture at the location P2 of the operation point OP1970 corresponds to a faster flame speed and favors the kernel growth, which has grown significantly larger than the other kernels. This result confirms that the G -equation combustion model used in this work is capable of taking into account differences in the conditions at the ignition location from the very beginning of the flame growth. These differences may also affect the ignition delay and the ignition location along the spark channel, which is taken into account by the ignition model proposed in this work.

The last results discussed in this section are the reaction progress profiles at the plane cut through the combustion chamber shown in Fig. 7.33 and the comparison between the calculated and measured pressure and ROHR profiles presented in Fig. 7.34. Although these results do not concern the ignition process directly, it is worth to discuss the flame propagation from the two distinct ignition points through the combustion chamber of the PAMAR-4 engine and how the combination of the proposed ignition model and the G -equation combustion model performs in the investigated cases. The evolution of the reaction progress in Fig. 7.33 corresponds to the flame propagation — the red color is the burnt mixture, the blue color is the fresh mixture and the transition between them corresponds to the flame front (and the G -surface in the combustion model). For the operation point OP1970, the rich mixture in the crevice of the port P4 initially burns rapidly, as already presented in Fig. 7.31. After the initial expansion the flame ignited

at the location P4 reaches the very lean mixture in the surrounding area and is slowed down. On the other hand, the flame ignited at the location P2 propagates through the combustion chamber and merges with the flame propagating from P4 to form a single flame front. It can be concluded that most of the heat released during the combustion process is due to the flame ignited and propagating from the location P2. For the operation point OP2245, the more uniform fuel distribution results in a similar flame propagation from the two opposite ignition locations. Two flame fronts also merge together close to the end of the combustion process.

Figure 7.33: Numerical results of the reaction progress in the PAMAR-4 engine.

The flame propagation in the two investigated cases has an effect on the ROHR and pressure profiles given in Fig. 7.34. The flame effectively propagating only from the location P2 in the operation point OP1970 results in a lower maximum of the ROHR than in the operating point OP2245 where two similar flame fronts propagate from the two opposite locations. This corresponds to a lower gradient of the pressure rise in the case OP1970 than in the case OP2245. The whole combustion process also lasts longer for the operating point OP1970. What is important to notice is that in both cases the calculation results match the pressure profile with a very good agreement. Only the peak pressure in the operating point OP2245 is slightly underestimated. It is possible that in the experiment the mixture auto-ignites close to the end of the combustion process increasing the ROHR and the pressure, while in the simulations no auto-ignition model is included.

Figure 7.34: Measured and calculated pressure and ROHR for the considered operation points of the PAMAR-4 engine.

The results presented in this section confirm that the combination of the proposed ignition model with the G -equation combustion model is capable of an effective simulation of the combustion process also in a non-conventional engine configuration like the PAMAR-4 engine. The new ignition model is able to predict the ignition of the air-fuel mixture from the multiple spark plugs at discrete locations in the combustion chamber. While the ignition model provides multiple ignition points, the G -equation combustion model calculates the propagation of the distinct flame fronts which can merge together to form a single flame front in the combustion chamber.

Chapter 8

Summary and conclusions

In this work the new predictive spark ignition model has been developed and implemented into the AVL FireTM solver for 3D CFD combustion simulations in IC engines. The development of the new ignition model has been preceded by the literature review on the spark ignition phenomenon, its experimental investigations and numerical modeling.

The spark discharge can be divided into three phases — plasma breakdown, arc discharge and glow discharge which all have particular electrical properties and heat losses. As a result only a part of the energy deposited into the plasma channel is available for the initiation of combustion. The inflammation of the mixture by the spark plasma is a complicated phenomenon itself. The high temperatures in the center of the spark channel preclude the existence of stable combustion products. The steep temperature gradients that occur at the plasma surface imply considerable gradients in concentrations of radicals which contribute to the flame initiation. The heat and radicals transferred from the spark towards unburned mixture combined with fairly suitable temperatures for the formation of stable molecules lead to an acceleration of the combustion reactions at the outer plasma surface. All of these processes are strongly dependent on the electrodes temperature, geometry (width, shape and gap size), local flow field, turbulence or spark energy and power affecting the flame kernel formation. After the spark deposition chemical reactions must produce enough energy to overcome heat losses or quenching of the flame kernel can occur.

The ignition of air-fuel mixture by a spark discharge has been widely investigated in the past and is well understood. However, the complicity of the spark ignition process makes numerical modeling of this phenomenon a very challenging task. It is desirable to model all phenomena occurring during the spark ignition to reflect the real process

as close as possible. However, it would require resolution of very short time scales and very small length scales leading to very fine meshes and time steps in CFD solvers, what may not be practical in commercial engineering applications. Therefore, usually simplified phenomenological models of the spark ignition and early flame kernel formation are developed and implemented in CFD solvers. In order to account for the details of the ignition process, these models are usually based on the tracking of the particles that represent the spark arc, flame kernels or early flame surface propagation independently on the grid size. The review of the spark ignition models for 3D CFD combustion modeling in Chapter 5 revealed that in the individual models particular aspects of the ignition phenomenon are described in detail, while others are taken into account in a simplified manner or even completely omitted. For example, the DPIK model neglects the spark channel structure and does not monitor the mixture locally for ignitability. In the AKTIM model, the spark channel is represented by computational particles, but the direct link to the position of the flame kernel is missing. Both the SparkCIMM and CADIM models ignore the time-dependent energy deposition by the spark into the mixture and treat it as a constant in time, which has been proved to be incorrect for high velocity flows where the spark is deflected significantly. This shows that there is still space for improvements in the field of spark ignition modeling and it is desirable to develop new and more accurate ignition models for 3D CFD combustion modeling.

The ignition model proposed in this work builds upon several studies on the ignition process and integrates submodels for the individual phenomena of the spark ignition. The submodels for the electrical circuit of the ignition system, spark plasma dynamics, heat transfer from the spark towards surrounding mixture, ignition delay of the mixture and early flame kernel growth are coupled together to form one comprehensive ignition model. The development and implementation of the individual submodels has been described in detail in Chapter 6. The new ignition model allows to predict the temporal development and deflection of the spark plasma channel, the ignition delay time and the position of the initial flame kernel. In comparison to other approaches, a more detailed physical model is developed to accurately describe each phenomenon and gain a more complete understanding of the spark-ignition process in SI engines. The proposed model has been implemented into the AVL FireTM software in the context of the *G*-equation combustion model and can be accessed by the user under the name AVL-CADIM. The

name comes from the CADIM ignition model [8], which provided the idea of calculating the temperature diffusion normal to the surface of the spark. Several improvements to the CADIM that have been implemented, such as the model of the electrical circuit, the advanced model of the spark channel dynamics, the possibility of restrikes or modeling ignition from multiple spark plugs, resulted in the new and original ignition model. The new ignition model, its implementation and initial results were presented by the author in [81].

The new model has been widely validated against experimental data in order to verify its capability of the spark ignition modeling. Firstly, the spark discharge process in a strong flow field has been modeled and the results compared to the experiment. The available experimental data included visual measurements of the spark channel with a high-speed camera and measurements of the current and voltage in the secondary circuit of the ignition system for three different velocities generated at the spark gap — 8 m/s, 12 m/s and 16 m/s. In all three cases the model correctly predicted the duration of the discharge process with multiple breakdowns, the deflection of the spark during the first breakdown, the current and voltage in the electrical circuit and the power supplied to the spark arc which is important for calculation of the temperature at the surface of the spark channel and the ignition delay of the mixture. Small deviations from the experiment in the second and consecutive spark breakdowns have been noticed and explained by the fact that in the experiment the spark deposited after the restrike is already elongated and deflected, while the model does not include the stochastic character of restrikes and initializes the new spark channel directly between the electrodes after the restrike. Nevertheless, a very good agreement with the experiment during the first breakdown of the spark confirmed that the model can be used in engine cases, where the ignition is also expected to take place during the first breakdown of the spark. The results of the spark discharge modeling in a strong flow field were presented by the author in [82]. Secondly, the new ignition model combined with the G -equation combustion model has been applied for modeling the AVL FM540 research engine. The results of pressure profile in the cylinder, ROHR and CA50 have been compared to the experimentally measured values for four engine operation points obtaining a satisfactory agreement. The investigated cases considered the engine running with different rotational speeds — 1250 rpm, 1500 rpm, 2000 rpm and 3000 rpm. The deflection of the spark channel calculated with the model was only

moderate in the first two cases, more evident in the third case and the most significant in the last case where the velocity at the spark gap reached 7 m/s. Each case has been additionally calculated without the ignition model, simply initializing the flame kernel between the spark electrodes at the ignition timing to show the influence of the ignition model on the overall result. Results have shown that for the low rotational speed close to 1000 rpm the ignition delay calculated with the ignition model corresponds only to around 1 degCA and has a small effect on the overall result. However, for 3000 rpm the same delay already corresponds to around 2 – 3 degCA, while for 6000 rpm it could be close to 6 degCA considerably advancing the ignition and leading to overestimated peak pressures in the cylinder. It shows that the new ignition model may be of particular importance in modeling high rotational speed engines. Finally, the ignition model has been used in modeling of the PAMAR-4 Opposed-Piston research engine. Although the low rotational speed of the considered operation points would not reveal the benefits of the ignition model, the other properties of the PAMAR-4 engine, such as two spark plugs per cylinder and a non-conventional shape of the combustion chamber, are interesting from the combustion modeling point of view. Results of the pressure profile and ROHR have shown that the new ignition model is capable of correctly calculating ignition from multiple spark plugs, while the *G*-equation combustion model can independently handle the flame propagation from multiple ignition points occurring in distinct locations in the combustion chamber. The numerical results of the PAMAR-4 engine obtained with the proposed ignition model were presented by the author in [83]. The final implementation of the model and verification of its performance with experimental data were presented by the author in [84].

To conclude, the new and comprehensive ignition model has been developed and implemented into the AVL FireTM code to predict the ignition process for the *G*-equation combustion model. The results obtained in various cases have verified numerically that the proposed model is capable of the correct reproduction of the spark ignition process and overall engine performance. Any user of the AVL FireTM software can apply the new model in their simulations. Currently, the work is ongoing on the connection of the proposed ignition model with the other combustion models in the AVL FireTM software (ECFM, ECFM-3Z, Lagrangian Flame Tracking, General Gas Phase Reactions).

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